

AQUAFUSION: AN IOT-BASED AQUAPONICS MONITORING SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

AquaFusion: An IoT-Based Aquaponics Monitoring System

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Aquaponics closely resembles hydroponics but with an aspect of aquaculture added to it by adding a pond, reservoir, or tank to house aquatic creatures bred and farmed in it. Though some innovations and improvements to enhance the yields of aquaponics farming methods further, its digitalization still needs to be. This application aims to design and develop an IoT-based sensor-equipped system “AquaFusion”, that monitors the ambient conditions needed in an aquaponics farm. This application will also include real-time display of sensor values in graphical and numerical manner. This application was designed iteratively, creating test scenarios to ensure that the user’s requirements were met. The requirements were collected via structured interview and online survey questionnaires were treated using focus group method, which easily summarizes the qualitative data to determine the respondents’ reactions and summary statistics. As a result of the survey, the proponents found out that farmers are struggling to maintain and to produce more yield since monitoring the ambient condition values is so much laborious and time consuming. The inaccuracy of measuring the values results to poor yields and costly maintenance. This leads to the conclusion that AquaFusion is a great tool to help farmers to automate task and accurately monitor real time values that are crucial to increase yield and maintain accurate conditions.

Keywords: Aquaponics, IoT-based sensor-equipped system, farmers, ambient conditions, sensor values

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DEDICATION

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CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

The agricultural and fishery industries in the Philippines are one of the primary food sources for the domestic market and extend through the markets of its neighboring nations. Although the Philippines is in the ranks of being a newly industrialized country, by itself, it is not considered wholly an agricultural country internationally, as opposed to the views of many Filipinos. Agriculture, fisheries, and forestry are big industries, and 8.9% of the country's GDP by sector is from exports only. Worldwide, the Philippines is known as the eighth largest producer of rice, with an output of 19,294,856 metric tons (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2023). Other than rice, other significant crops stapling for some people are corn, cassava, and sweet potatoes. Common vegetables and root crops like ampalaya, eggplant, cabbage, tomatoes, and potatoes are also prevalent and are planted depending on the crop season (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2023).

Aquaponics closely resembles hydroponics but with an aspect of aquaculture added to it by adding a pond, reservoir, or tank to house aquatic creatures bred and farmed in it. In this method, the growth medium used is still water; however, instead of using biomass and different minerals, the nitrogenous droppings from the aquatic animals mixed with different chemical compounds collected with the water would be used (Arellano, 2021). Though some innovations and improvements to enhance the yields of aquaponics farming methods further, its digitalization still needs to be. Chemical and pH levels testing for hydroponics and systems that use water mostly use chemical-based testing kits to check and monitor each system occasionally (Go Green Aquaponics, 2021). Hence, this paper focuses on digitizing its methods so that its users can view it, monitor the system in real time, and increase the yields of individual aquaponics systems.

Rationale of the Study

The success of an aquaponics system relies on the correct management and implementation of sensors, IoT techniques, and intelligent systems. In more developed industries (such as automotive, manufacturing, and construction), an automated system has increased productivity, decreased human error, and shortened labor times. Extrapolating it to aquaponics will enable the concept of precision farming to be realized with the inherent benefits of increased resource efficiency (water, electricity, fertilizers), decreased field expertise, reduced human intervention, and even accelerated crop growth for most crops because the ideal environment can be automatically maintained (Yanes, 2020).

Because the aquaponics system does not need soil, uses a small amount of water and land area, can grow fresh produce in any climate, and uses much less energy than traditional agriculture

(Kyaw & Ng, 2017). Producing "fish" and "vegetables" simultaneously is possible in an aquaponics system. As a result, the aquaponics system will be one of the preferred systems for sustainable farming. In addition, compared to conventional agriculture, which requires farming on the ground, the aquaponics system significantly reduces labor (Lakhiar et al., 2020).

The application of automation in agriculture is known as precision agriculture, which aims to collect, process, and analyze temporal, spatial, and plant morphological features along with other information to support management choices for maximizing growth inputs and protecting resources regarding water and nutrients. Aquaponics systems incorporating automation have shorter production times, require less labor to operate, produce better products, and are more sustainable. If it is monitored and managed by modern technologies like IoT and ICT, it is used as precision technology (Qiu, 2022).

Philippine agriculture is frequently associated with antiquated farming practices and manual methods. Between 2016 and 2019, the Philippines' agricultural sector grew by a meager 1.3% (The World Bank, 2020). The government and the private sectors have been researching to foster innovations that address these over the years, and a current comprehensive guide map for farmers is one of the examples. This map identifies the best crop to cultivate for each specific section of land across the country. Essential fertilizer requirements of areas are also provided (Mogato, 2018). Despite all of these technologies, hunger is spreading across the globe annually. Because Filipino farmers to using traditional farming methods, the country's agricultural growth could have been a more active and effective adaptation of these technologies is still nebulous (Aquino et al., 2020).

Globally, there are currently thousands of small-scale aquaponics projects and several larger-scale, commercial, or nearly commercial enterprises, primarily in the United States, specifically Hawaii. Much research on integrated multi-trophic aquaculture involves growing fish and plants in more open systems in addition to aquaponics. The traditional examples in this context involve raising caged salmon near the cultivation of mussels and seaweed. However, despite extensive pilot-scale research for well over a decade, these systems have not been widely adopted on a commercial level, primarily due to the large quantity and low value of seaweed produced, decreased water circulation around the fish cages, and a variety of other management issues (Mohamad et al., 2013).

Numerous studies have utilized various Internet of Things (IoT) systems in compact lab setups for the best growth of plants in hydroponic and aquaponic environments. Valiente et al. (2018) built a system to measure pH and water temperature for growing romaine lettuce and Nile tilapia. They built an actuation system to keep the pH level between 6.2 and 7.5 and the water

temperature between 27 and 30 °C to ensure optimal growth. Yanes et al. (2020) reviewed IoT and intelligent systems for nitrite concentrations, electroconductivity, dissolved oxygen, and hardness in the aquaponic solution to ensure a viable business model in small-scale semi-automated systems. Mahanta et al. (2022) applied various concentrations of plasma-activated water at various voltages and time intervals to the seeds in a thorough comparative study on the growth of soybeans in hydroponic solution to reduce heavy metal uptake and ensure better yield. However, little work to develop data-driven strategies to control the essential nutrients for growing fish and plants; this is the main driving force behind this paper.

The researchers' proposed IoT-based aquaponic monitoring system, "AquaFusion," is an automated system designed to enhance efficiency and alleviate the workload of aquaponic farmers. The system intends to monitor remotely and control critical parameters, reducing the need for constant physical presence. By providing real-time, accurate information on water quality, nutrient levels, and system performance, AquaFusion minimizes the risk of human errors and improves overall farming efficiency. The system optimizes resource management, promotes sustainability, and reduces operational costs by promptly detecting and addressing parameter deviations. By implementing AquaFusion, aquaponic farmers and practitioners can focus on critical aspects of farming while ensuring high-quality production and maintaining a healthy environment for fish and plants.

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to design and develop AquaFusion, an IoT-based sensor-equipped system that monitors the ambient conditions needed in an aquaponics farm. In order to achieve this aim, the study seeks to address the following specific objectives:

1. To gather data about the problems and difficulties pertaining to the key parameters in maintaining the ambient conditions of the aquaponic farm.
2. To develop an IoT-based mechanism for optimal monitoring allowing automation of the aquaponic system; and
3. To identify a notification system for timely alerts on critical parameter deviations.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

The system focuses on monitoring the development and deployment of a comprehensive monitoring solution for aquaponic systems. It aims to monitor critical parameters such as water quality (pH, temperature, turbidity, level) and system performance metrics. It allows farmers and aquaponic practitioners to track and analyze data to ensure optimal fish and plant growth

conditions. The hardware device caters only one tuna box of semi-Kratky and NFT Method of Aquaponic setup. It also allows automated alerts and notifications to address deviations or potential issues within the aquaponic system promptly. The system will support data analysis and visualization, offering insights into the system's performance. It will provide a user-friendly interface of mobile and web applications that allows users to access and interpret data easily.

The system has limitations that need consideration. Sensor availability and compatibility may restrict the system's effectiveness. Complex dynamics within aquaponic systems limit understanding of subtle changes. The cost and scalability of the system may impose financial constraints—technical expertise for optimal utilization—environmental variations, like weather and water source changes. Integration with existing systems may need help with compatibility issues. Recognizing and addressing these limitations appropriately is crucial for successfully implementing and utilizing the system in aquaponic environments.

Significance of the Study

The system holds significant importance for various stakeholders involved in aquaponic farming. The following are the key areas where the study's findings can have a positive impact:

Farmers and Aquaponic Practitioners. The study provides farmers and aquaponic practitioners with a comprehensive monitoring system to optimize their systems, leading to improved productivity, resource management, and plant and fish growth.

Environmental Sustainability. The study promotes sustainable aquaponic practices by ensuring optimal water quality, nutrient levels, and ecological balance, minimizing environmental pollution risks.

Research and Innovation. The study fosters research and innovation by evaluating the monitoring system, enabling the development of advanced engagement techniques, devices, and methodologies for addressing health issues and enhancing system performance.

Health and Consumer Safety. The study ensures the safety and quality of aquaponic-grown produce, benefiting consumers, particularly those with respiratory conditions, by providing safe and nutritious food.

The Researchers. The study increases the researchers' ability, expertise, and experience in agriculture, aquaculture, and IoT-based technologies that maximizes the capabilities of automating manual monitoring for farmers and aquaponic practitioners.

Future Researchers. The study guarantees their research on aquaponic issues and the problems of manual monitoring in their respective farms, and research guarantees the workplace provided by the users and practitioners.

Flow of the Study

This diagram shows the study's different inputs, processes, and outputs.

Figure 1: **Flow of the Study**

Figure 1 shows the flow of the study of AquaFusion. First, researchers gathered data about the problems and difficulties of farmers or aquaponic practitioners and developed an IoT-based monitoring and notification system. Then, researchers used a lean method that corresponds to these proponents: define value, value map streaming, and create flow and perfection. These proponents will be applied to create applications for AquaFusion.

Definition of Terms

This section contains the specific meaning of the following terms concerning the context used to clarify the study more.

Aquaponics. It refers to a sustainable farming method combining aquaculture and hydroponics in a symbiotic environment.

Ambient Conditions. It refers to the environmental factors surrounding the aquaponic system.

Automation. It refers to the tasks and processes within the aquaponic system that are technology automated.

Data Analysis. It refers to examining collected data to derive insights and make informed decisions.

IoT (Internet of Things). It refers to interconnected devices with sensors and connectivity for data collection and exchange.

Monitoring System. It refers to the hardware and software components for collecting and analyzing real-time data on water quality, nutrient levels, and system performance.

Notification System. It refers to a mechanism in the aquaponic system that provides timely alerts or notifications.

Parameters. It refers to the measurable factors influencing the aquaponic system, such as water temperature, pH, and nutrient concentrations.

Parameter Deviation. It refers to the variances or deviations from the desired or optimal values of specific parameters from the aquaponic system.

pH Level. It measures how basic or acidic the water is depending on the dissolved chemical compounds in the aquaponic system.

Remote Monitoring. It refers to the ability to remotely access real-time data from sensors and devices remotely, enabling remote tracking and adjustments.

Resource Management. It refers to the strategic utilization and conservation of resources within the aquaponic system.

Sustainability. It refers to maintaining ecological balance, resource efficiency, and minimal environmental impact within the aquaponic system.

System Performance. It refers to the overall efficiency and effectiveness of the aquaponic system, including fish and plant growth, nutrient cycling, and water quality.

Kratky Method. It refers to the method of a passive hydroponic technique for growing plants suspended above a reservoir of nutrient rich water.

NFT Method. It refers to the recirculating of nutrient solution stored in a tank by means of an electric pump through channels with a flat surface.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

This chapter discusses the related literature and studies following the researchers' careful and in-depth research. The framework of the study comprises the main focus of the research described in the thesis. This review establishes a foundation for our research on how our approach contributes to the existing methodologies of previous studies.

Theoretical Background

This study anchored towards the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), which explains the consumer acceptance of aquaponics products as innovative green products that have been examined with close-ended questionnaires in Malaysia by (Tamin et al., 2015). From a set of different behavior-influencing factors (relative advantage, compatibility, subjective norm, perceived knowledge, self-efficacy, and trust), two factors have a significant impact: Relative advantage and perceived knowledge. The relative advantage describes how far buying behavior is by superior product qualities compared to conventional products. The aquaponics products are fresh and healthy, and this perception led to a buying advantage. The perceived knowledge relates to how much the customer knows about the production method. The more familiar the customers were with the method, the more likely the consumers were willing to buy aquaponic products.

There was no correlation in the category subjective norm, which relates to how much the opinion of friends and family influences the buying decision. Interestingly there was no correlation for the factor of compatibility. This factor relates to how much the product buying experience is compatible with the customer's lifestyle. The product-to-market process in Malaysia is not very different for aquaponics products and conventional products, so while it is questionable whether the results of this study to European markets, a base message is that education about the production method and communicating the beneficial effects regarding the freshness of the food and the benefits for the environment are essential marketing activities (Tamin et al., 2015).

The Theory of Technological Innovation System (TIS) supports the Theory of Planned Behavior, which Carlsson and Stankiewicz popularized. It is an "institutional alignment" in the formative phase of a TIS if institutions are sufficiently aligned with market form and provide space for entrepreneurial experimentation to determine commercially viable paths for implementing the technology (Bergek et al., 2008, pp. 407-409). For institutional alignment to take place, the proponents of the new technology need to be sufficiently organized to contribute to a process of "legitimation" of their technology (König et al. 2018).

Both theories highlight the importance of perceived advantages, knowledge, and institutional alignment in influencing the acceptance and adoption of aquaponics products. Education about the production method, communication of benefits, and organizational efforts are crucial for promoting consumer acceptance and creating a supportive environment for implementing aquaponics technology.

Related Literature

Aquaponics combines hydroponics and recirculating aquaculture, a promising solution to the negative environmental impacts of intensive fish and crop production (Rakocy et al., 2003). In these integrated systems, nutrients are excreted by fish or generated by microbial activity in hydroponically cultured plants, which treat the water before it is recycled to the fish tank (Endut et al., 2009). Aquaponics has received considerable attention due to its ability to sustain water quality, minimize freshwater consumption, and provide a marketable vegetation crop (Danaher et al., 2011). However, few microbial studies determine food safety status, suggesting that further research is needed to evaluate this aspect (Elumalai et al., 2017).

Aquaponics is a complex and atypical food production technology due to its integrative character and multiple application scenarios from high-tech to low-tech (König et al., 2016). It is a sustainable agricultural production system that can help to reduce production process inefficiencies by designing systems that close nutrient cycles—one of the main aspects of aquaponics, a combination of aquaculture and hydroponics. In aquaponics, the waste produced by the fish fertilizes the plants, and the plants clean the water for the fish (Goddek et al., 2015). This closed system can be very efficient regarding water and nutrient use and produce various crops, including vegetables, fruits, and herbs (Francis et al., 2003).

Coupled aquaponics is the archetype form of aquaponics. The technical complexity increases with the production scale and required water treatment, e.g., filtration, UV light for microbial control, automatic controlled feeding computerization, and biosecurity. It is upscaling through a multiunit system that allows several hydroponics subsystems. The main task of coupled aquaponics is the purification of aquaculture process water through the integration of plants which add economic benefits to suitable species like herbs, medicinal plants, or ornamentals (Palm et al., 2018).

Aquaponics holds great promise for meeting the world's increasing food demand (Goddek et al., 2015). The hydroponic component directly influences water quality, essential for fish rearing (Yavuzcan et al., 2017). It is also the primary source of water loss by plant evapotranspiration. Because the design and operation of the hydroponic system influence the sustainability of the entire

process, either directly in terms of water consumption or indirectly in terms of system management costs, particular attention should be paid to it (Maucieri et al., 2018).

Research conducted by Ambrosio et al. (2019) at De La University, Philippines, aims to provide an accessible, low-maintenance, and sustainable food source for condominium residents as an alternative to market goods—many condominium buildings in the past few years in Metro Manila because of the growing urban population. Metro Manila has studio-type condominium units of less than 50 square meters (about twice the parking space area) (Mercurio, 2017). Their results show 100% accuracy in the modification of the parameters in the system. The actuators could maintain the parameters' values within the desired ranges. With this, successful automation in the aquaponic system.

Subsequently, Rayos et al. (2022) stated in their research that urban aquaponics is one of the new developments projects the Government of the Philippines implemented. The DA-BFAR conducted a social cost-benefit analysis in 2020 to assess the costs and benefits of urban aquaponics, considering its social impacts. Their findings help people decide to invest in urban aquaponics, especially when there is a need for action to address food security, health safety, and income opportunity while the world is still facing a pandemic. The results showed that the benefits outweighed the costs and risks of investing in urban aquaponics.

Internet of Things (IoT) devices and systems are gaining popularity in the aquaponic industry because of their low cost and ease of use. They can be supervised and controlled at home or any place using the Internet (Valiente et al., 2018). The fish and plants can be grown optimally in a controlled environment in automated aquaponics. Although existing IoT-driven aquaponic applications have been studied and made, new technology-based solutions are still required to meet the industry's demands in Aquaponics (Prabha et al., 2020).

Supriadi et al. (2019) put forward the concept of the usage of commonly used IoT devices and sensors in an aquaponics sensor in a method to effectively intercommunicate and combine the different sensors to effectively control the system's ecosystem and rectify the tank environment if a drop in pH level increase in different chemical concentration or a rise or drop in temperature is detected.

IoT aims to provide a continuous presence of distinct cyber-physical systems incorporating intelligence capabilities (Marques, 2019). On the one hand, IoT has changed people's daily routines and is today included in most social activities and, in particular, regarding the intelligent city concept (Gubbi et al., 2013). On the other hand, IoT is a relevant architecture for designing and developing intelligent monitoring systems for water quality assessment. IoT is currently applied in

different monitoring activities, such as thermal comfort, acoustic comfort, and air quality (Marques & Pitarma, 2019).

Moreover, IoT is also applied in agricultural environments such as aquaponics and hydroponics (Ruengittinun et al., 2017). Water quality is crucial in agricultural activities and significantly affects the productivity and efficiency of agricultural ecosystems. IoT systems for enhanced water quality allow to store and compare the water quality data to support the decision-making of agricultural plant managers. Alongside the advantage of automation, IoT has led to using adaptive and responsive systems in water quality monitoring. These intelligent systems can alert authorities or personnel regarding impending dangers, such as the high-water level of an impending flood, or non-optimal conditions, such as in aquaponic systems (Gubbi et al., 2013).

In addition, data acquisition plays a vital role in IoT. In conjunction with the previously given systems, Supriadi et al. (2019) system also provides a methodology not only focused on the monitoring and rectification of the system but also adds the capabilities of effective data collection with their system's effective use of the Raspberry Pi microcomputer in addition to the use of having Raspberry Pi as an implement of controlling balance to different components found in the IoT system. Sporting a powerful ARM SoC (System on a chip), it does not only limit itself as a procedural pre-programmed system designed to do specific work, but it can also handle networking capabilities together with an option to implement a variety of high-level programming languages of choice which gives it a capability to also communicate with other IoT devices and computers (Avenwedde, 2022).

Aquaponics demonstrates potential for sustainable food production, integrating hydroponics, aquaculture, and IoT technologies, offering efficient monitoring and management opportunities. Further research is needed to ensure food safety, optimize system design, and explore the full potential of automation and IoT in aquaponics.

Related Studies

Junge et al. (2017) conducted an empirical study on the strategic points in aquaponics. The knowledge of the factors that determine the commercial viability of aquaponics has significantly expanded in recent years, and it is their conviction that this technology has the potential to play a significant role in food production in the future. However, aquaponics has environmental, operational, and socioeconomic effects. The points raised in their contribution illustrate additional research on the biological and technological system per se. It should also involve system design and socioeconomic aspects and their interrelation for developing aquaponics as a technology contributing to more sustainable food systems.

Keesman et al. (2019) studied Aquaponics System Modelling on the appropriate model complexity that meets the experimental data for estimating parameters and states that allows them to answer questions related to the modeling objective, such as simulation, experiment design, prediction, and control—the issue of modeling aquaponic systems in their study. In aquaponics, modeling for different objectives: (i) insight/understanding, (ii) analysis, (iii) estimation, and (iv) management and control. For all these objectives, appropriate models. For example, to achieve objectives (ii) and (iii), an empirical approach can be utilized, which uses statistical models to analyze data from previous experimental trials to extract as much information as possible without conducting new experiments. Statistical models can reveal the most critical factors affecting fish and crop production in aquaponics systems. Future experiments could concentrate on these factors, thus making the utilization of costly research assets more effective. Simulation of aquaponics with the mathematical models under a wide range of management conditions will improve the understanding of aquaponics, verify different aquaponics configurations and point the way to the most promising strategies for improving aquaponics facilities. Again, this can lead to a more efficient way of conducting experiments.

De Graaf & Goddek (2019) conducted Smarthood research to quantify the degree of flexibility and self-sufficiency that an aquaponics-integrated microgrid can provide. The results are promising since it is inherent in the aquaponic system because of high thermal mass, flexible pumps, and adaptive lighting; the overall degree of self-sufficiency is 95.38% making it nearly wholly self-sufficient and grid independent. With the aquaponics system being responsible for 38.3% of power consumption and 51.4% of heat consumption, the impact of the aquaponics facility on the total system's energy balance is very high.

A study by Kyaw et al. (2017) designed and develop an intelligent aquaponics system that can synergize fish farming and plant growing. Various sensors, actuators, microcontrollers, and microprocessors were employed in the system to monitor and control water quality, light intensity, and fish feed. Early warnings include email, short message service, and push notifications. The user can also monitor the aquaponics facilities from a web application through a camera module of the system. Their study has demonstrated self-sustainable, cost-effective, and eco-friendly urban farming that can attract commercial farmers, aquaponic farmers, and home gardeners. A large-scale implementation can significantly reduce labor and operating costs while increasing livestock production and profitability, contributing to sustainable and livable cities.

These studies highlight the potential of aquaponics as an innovative and sustainable food production system. Further research is needed to understand the environmental and socioeconomic aspects, optimize system design and modeling, and explore the integration of aquaponics with other

technologies for enhanced efficiency and self-sufficiency. These findings provide valuable insights for the development and advancement of aquaponics in contributing to more sustainable food systems.

Comparative Matrix

A comparison matrix compares commodities, services, and more abstract notions like strategies and ideas. The matrix also organizes and categorizes the items.

Table 1

COMPARATIVE MATRIX

This section provides an overview of related studies and literature findings from similar studies to which the current proposed study is related or as similarities.

Related Studies	Features	Limitations	Platform	Support	Monetization Scheme
Name: Coupled Aquaponic Systems URL: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-15943-6_7 Year: 2018 Proponents(s): 1. Harry W. Palm 2. Ulrich Knaus 3. Samuel Appelbaum 4. Sebastian M. Strauch 5. Benz Kotzen	Coupled aquaponic systems do not necessarily use mechanical particulate filtering in the classical sense and the keep consistent nutrient flow between the aquaculture and hydroponic units.	Its disadvantage is managing the fecal load in the coupled aquaponic system where the plants absorb the nutrients, and filter presses or geotextiles can remove particulate waste.	Web-based interface accessible on browsers	Online documentation and user guides	Additional revenue through sales of compatible IoT sensors and accessories

Table 1.1
COMPARATIVE MATRIX CONT'D

Related Studies	Features	Limitations	Platform	Support	Monetization Scheme
<p>Name: Aquaponic Systems Modeling URL: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-15943-6_11 Year: 2019 Proponents(s):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Karel J. Jeesman 2. Oliver Körner 3. Kai Wagner 4. Jan Urban, 5. Divas Karimanzira 6. Thomas Rauschenbach 7. Simon Goddek 	Shows the links between the subsystems so that a complete Aquaponic systems model can be built and integrated into daily practice concerning management and control of Aquaponic systems	To choose an appropriate model complexity that meets the experimental data for estimation of parameters and states parameter estimation with primary data that use a more significant number of aquaponics facilities.	Web-based interface accessible on browsers	Online documentation and user guides	N/A
<p>Name: Smarthoods: Aquaponics Integrated Microgrids URL: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-15943-6_15 Year: 2019 Proponents(s):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Florijn de Graaf 2. Simon Goddek 	Integrates a neighborhood microgrid with an urban agriculture facility that houses a decoupled multi-loop aquaponics facility.	Regulators must find ways to facilitate local energy markets to unlock the full potential of highly integrated microgrids.	Web-based interface accessible on browsers	Online documentation and user guides	Additional revenue through sales of compatible IoT sensors and accessories

Table 1.2
COMPARATIVE MATRIX CONT'D

Related Studies	Features	Limitations	Platform	Support	Monetization Scheme
<p>Name: Smart Aquaponics System for Urban Farming URL: https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1876610217364585 Year: 2017 Proponents(s):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Thu Ya Kyaw 2. Andrew Keong Ng 	<p>The system integrates readily found sensors, everyday devices, and free software to build an aquaponics system that can support urban farming at a dynamic scale.</p>	<p>The system does not initially include the support of sophisticated sensors for its design in testing the water quality like dissolved oxygen.</p>	<p>Web-based interface accessible on browsers and an android mobile application</p>	<p>Online documentation and user guides</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Name: Urban Aquaponics URL: https://repository.seafdec.org/handle/20.500.12066/7119 Year: 2022 Proponent(s):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Joseph Christopher Rayos 2. Elymi-AR-J Subang-Tunacao 3. Imelda Calixto Angelica Rose Lopez 	<p>Cost-efficient urban aquaculture technology using solar-powered aquaponics.</p>	<p>The system will be significantly affected by adverse weather conditions and fluctuation of market prices.</p>	<p>Traditional Farm</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>Positive cash flow, sales and profits of vegetables and fish.</p>

AquaFusion has similarities to the related literature above. It focuses on integrating aquaponic systems, which involves combining aquaculture and hydroponics to create a symbiotic environment for the cultivation of plants and the breeding of aquatic animals. It emphasizes the importance of system modeling, management, and control. It aims to develop models and frameworks that enable effective management and control of aquaponic systems, ensuring optimal performance and productivity. The system also utilizes sensors and various technologies to monitor

and collect data depending on various factors and parameters within the aquaponic systems. Data for analysis, decision-making, and improving system efficiency.

AquaFusion also has differences in their specific areas of focus within aquaponics. “Coupled Aquaponic Systems” concentrates on the absence of mechanical particulate filtering and maintaining consistent nutrient flow between aquaculture and hydroponic units. In contrast, “Aquaponic System Modeling” aims to establish a complete aquaponic systems model that can be into daily management and control practices. “Smarthoods: Aquaponics Integrated Microgrids” explores the integration of aquaponics with a neighborhood microgrid, highlighting the relationship between urban agriculture and energy systems. On the other hand, “Smart Aquaponics System for Urban Farming” prioritizes the integration of readily available sensors, everyday devices, and free software to develop a scalable aquaponic system that supports urban farming.

AquaFusion offers a unique and comprehensive solution to monitor and optimize nutrient levels in aquaponic systems. This system gathers essential data on critical parameters such as water pH level, water level, water turbidity, and water temperature, providing valuable insights into the overall health and balance of the system. What sets AquaFusion apart is the integration of IoT-based technology, enabling seamless communication between sensor nodes. To enhance user experience and system maintenance, AquaFusion also features a notification system using a web-based interface accessible in browsers for administrative controls and a mobile application that alerts users in real-time about critical parameter deviations and system malfunctions, facilitating prompt intervention and necessary adjustments. With its advanced features and functionalities, AquaFusion is a unique and innovative solution for optimizing aquaponic processes for improved productivity and sustainability.

CHAPTER III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter includes the procedures involved in creating the proposed system, and each figure focuses on each analysis and technical detail that support the proposal. It also includes the program workflow, diagrams, designs, future methodologies, resources, and tools for implementing "AquaFusion: An IoT-Based Aquaponics Monitoring System" to enhance efficiency and alleviate the workload of aquaponic farmers and practitioners. To help administrators make informed decisions about implementing a system, provide them with a clear understanding of its features, capabilities, risks, and challenges. It will help identify mitigation strategies and minimize the likelihood of problems.

Software Engineering Methodology

The AquaFusion application employs the Lean Method as the mainframe of the development of the system. The lean method supports maximizing diverse resources such as people, effort, and energy to give good value to the customers (Opinado, 2022). Like the other frameworks, the Lean method has its principles. These principles govern the entire framework to ensure that it completes its job. Do (2017) stated that the set of principles that the lean method follows are the following:

Figure 2: Lean Method Software Development Cycle

Value Phase. The researcher conducted extensive visits to various farms, engaging in interviews and distributing questionnaires to gather comprehensive insights. It involves gathering data on water pH levels, temperature, turbidity, level, humidity, and air temperature to determine their significance in maintaining optimal plant and fish growth conditions.

Value Stream Phase. The researcher utilized the collected data to design and implement the IoT solution, advancing the project's capabilities. that enable automated monitoring and data retrieval from the aquaponic system. It will eliminate manual data entry and ensure real-time access to critical information for decision-making.

Flow Phase. The researcher applied the developed IoT solution to achieve these objectives, improving functionality and performance. It includes setting up a notification system that alerts users in case of parameter deviations, enabling timely intervention and maintenance.

Pull Phase. The researcher implemented the developed IoT solution, which allowed users to access real-time data and make informed decisions. The system will provide personalized insights and recommendations based on individual user requirements.

Perfection Phase. The researcher leveraged user feedback and evolving needs to continue the ongoing improvements to the system, resulting in its continuous development. Regular evaluations and updates optimize system performance and enhance user experience, aiming for continuous improvement and perfection in monitoring.

Table 2
ITERATION PROCESS

Phase	Iteration 1	Iteration 2
Value	Identify critical parameters and metrics for monitoring the aquaponic system.	Determine specific user needs and requirements, such as aquaponic farmers and administrators.
Value Stream	Determine specific user needs and requirements, such as farmers and administrators.	Streamline data flow and eliminate unnecessary steps or bottlenecks.
Flow	Develop a seamless user interface and experience for accessing and interacting with the monitoring system.	Implement data flow mechanisms to ensure real-time data is continuously updated and displayed.

Table 2.1
ITERATION PROCESS CONT'D

Phase	Iteration 1	Iteration 2
Pull	Enable users to set personalized notification preferences based on specific thresholds and conditions.	Implement real-time alerts and notifications to inform users of critical parameter deviations.
Perfection	Continuously gather user feedback and data on system performance to identify areas for improvement.	Regularly update and optimize the monitoring system based on user needs and changing requirements.

Planning/Concept – Initiation Phase

The start phase marks the beginning of the project cycle. It makes high-level decisions about things like why a project is advantageous and what the needs are. It makes it possible for researchers to monitor the status of each need, the completion of assigned tasks, and deadlines. It also covers the cost of creating work schedules and starting new projects.

Business Model Canvas

This table shows how users of the AquaFusion application attempted to categorize business plans and activities as well as the organization's growth strategy and projected timeline. The Business Model Canvas (BMC) is a tool for illustrating the clients, market trajectory, value proposition, and financial aspects of a company's start-up.

Table 3
BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS

Key Partners	Key Activities	Value Proposition	Customer Relationships	Customer Segments
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aquaponics Suppliers/ Providers • Google Firebase API • Local agrivet/gardening/agriculture supplies stores • Local marine/aquatic supplies stores. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software Development/Engineering • Electronics Assembly/Manufacturing • Quality Testing • Device Calibration • Customer Servicing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide aquaponics systems owners and farmers the opportunity to integrate digitization of their systems. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Media • Toll-free hotline • Email 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small to medium-scale suburban aquaponics garden owners.

Table 3.1
BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS CONT'D

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MakerLab Electronics • Various 3rd party parts and component vendors online. 	<p>Key Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raspberry Pi Model B microcomputer • pH level, turbidity, temperature, and ultrasonic sensors. • Miscellaneous electronic components • Cloud service providers • Network subscription and connectivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simplifies labor and amount of work done for the system's maintenance. • Promotes the culture of the green/sustainable farming and agriculture. 	<p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online Platform/Web Application • Dedicated website • Social Media • Emails • Toll-free hotline 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consumers interested in home-farming tech • Government agriculture departments and programs
<p>Cost Structure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software Development/Engineering • Electronics Assembly/Manufacturing • Quality Testing • Online and Postpaid Subscriptions • Acquisition of sensors, microcomputer, and various electronic components. 		<p>Revenue Streams</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online Sales • Subscription-based • Device repair and servicing • Personalized Technical Support 		

Table 3 shows the business model canvas built on crucial partnerships with various suppliers and vendors. Our key activities include software development, electronics assembly, and customer support. The value proposition lies in simplifying aquaponics system maintenance and promoting sustainable farming. We connect with customers through social media, a toll-free hotline, and email. Our target customer segments include small, medium, and large-scale aquaponics farmers. Essential resources include Raspberry Pi microcomputers, sensors, and cloud services—channels like online platforms, websites, and social media to reach customers. Revenue streams come from online sales, subscriptions, and technical support fees. Our model aims to offer an efficient and digitized monitoring solution for aquaponics farmers.

Program Workflow

Program workflow shows the presentation of AquaFusion. The system application is a sequential, graphical form representing the guide for creating the designs. The workflow illustrates how the tasks are accomplished from start to end using standardized symbols and forms.

Figure 3: **Program Workflow (Aquaponic Farmer)**

Figure 3 shows the program workflow of the user in the AquaFusion application. It represents the user's sequence of execution and functionality. It enabled the programmers to plan the user's application architecture and functionalities. First, if the user does not have an account, the user will create an account by signing up and inputting their credentials. After logging in, the application will redirect the user to the sign-in page so that the user can proceed to the sensor menu page. If the user forgets the account password, the user will go to the forgot password page and input the registered email to the user's account. After the user's email is validated, the user will input the new account password to the sign-in page. The sensor menu page consists of two sub-tabs: sensor data values, which are the values of each sensor that are incorporated, and sensor status, which indicates the availability of each sensor. Under the sensor data values, it has a sensory data graph tab, enabling the user to monitor the results graphically instead of numerically. The plant monitoring page enables the users to monitor the results graphically. The profile page indicates the user's full name, the user's registered email, and the user's photo. The notification page enables the user to receive reports on all the existing monitoring pages on how the users behave and the indications, respectively. The Help and About Panel shows brief information about the application and FAQs and Technical Support Information which farmers, together with the technical support hotline, which the farmer can call when problems occur.

Figure 4: **Program Workflow (Farm Administrator)**

Figure 4 shows the program workflow of the administrator in the AquaFusion application. It represents the administrator's sequence of execution and functionality. It lets the programmers plan the farm administrator's application architecture and functionalities. First, suppose the farm administrator does not have an account. In that case, the farm administrator must create an account by contacting support and providing their credentials and the workgroup's name. After registration, the farm administrator can log in to their accounts. If the administrator has forgotten their account password, the farm administrator can reset their password by finding their workgroup name and providing their email. The farm administrator can log in and the admin dashboard page, which contains a variety of panels if the farm administrator successfully logs in. The dashboard panel will show a brief insight into the system's status. Next, the manage workgroup panel will show the options for a farm administrator to manage all the workgroup members of the aquaponics system. Next, the register farmer panel can directly register a farmer account on the system. Furthermore, lastly, for the user's category, one of the farm administrator's most essential tools, the harvest calendar, allows the farm administrator to manage the harvest schedules for the aquaponics system.

Here, the farm administrator can see and set the schedules for the farmers to follow.

On the other hand, for the system category, first, the notifications panel shows the current notification produced in the day. Next, the aquatic sensors status panel consists of the graph values of the status of the water, mainly the pH and turbidity are shown in this panel for a specific time and can be downloaded or exported in .csv format for better data management. In addition, the terrestrial sensor's status panel also functions similarly to the aquatic sensors' status panel. Next, the farm administrator also can change the system's thresholds through the threshold adjustment panel by the system's setup and configuration. Furthermore, lastly, the Technical Support panel will show frequently asked questions, the maintenance guide, and troubleshooting methods that the administrator and users can follow in the event of maintenance or troubleshooting.

Validation Board (Stage 1 and 2)

Table 4 is a visual presentation of a programmer's target market. It contains a problem, and its solution then determines which solution is the most useful and the riskiest assumption method.

Table 4
VALIDATION BOARD

	1	2
Programmer	Aquaponic Farmers	Farm Administrator
Problem	No capital to start aquaponic activities with no knowledge in smartphones and manual monitoring.	Challenges on efficiently managing of the system, including data collection, analysis and system maintenance.
Solution	Create a platform for aquaponic farmers that easily register and automate monitoring.	Develop an administration interface that allows access and management effectively.

Table 4.1
VALIDATION BOARD CONT'D

Programmer	Aquaponic Farmers	Farm Administrator
Riskiest Assumption	Neglection of manual labor since aquaponic farmers will only rely on our application	What if they need help to seamlessly navigate and utilize the administration interface, understand and interpret the collected data and effectively troubleshoot any technical issues?
Method & Success Criteria	90% of the respondents will be using this platform once it is available	90% of the respondents will be using this platform once it is available
Results and Destination	Persevere	Persevere
Learning	Farmers can utilize automation by eradicating external factors such as labor and workforce.	Administrators can be able to monitor their farmers and their medium effortlessly.

Table 4 shows the overview of the validation of AquaFusion. The problem shows the difficulty for aquaponic farmers when they have no capital or knowledge, and the administrator manages the system efficiently. The solution for this is by the help of the administrator itself by using information technology. The riskiest assumption shows the neglect of manual labor of the aquaponic farmers and, to the administrator, the supposition of seamless navigation and effective troubleshooting on any technical issues. Method and success criteria show the interested respondents in the application when released, and the result will persevere. While learning will promote positive outcomes for the target.

Gantt Chart

This section shows the list of the activities indicating the roles of each member and consists of the timeline of when it starts to finish. It will be edited and done by the technical writer to view each team's process.

Table 5
GANTT CHART

Task ID	Task Name	Task Lead	Start Date	End Date	Sept 2023				Oct 2023				Nov 2023				Dec 2023			
					1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
1	Identifying Critical Parameters for Monitoring	All Team	Sept 1, 2023	Sept 9, 2023	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
2	Schedule Implementation of IoT System	All Team	Sept 10, 2023	Sept 16, 2023	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
3	Organize Resource Allocation	Ursora	Sept 17, 2023	Sept 23, 2023	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
4	Procurement of Sensors	All Team	Sept 24, 2023	Sept 30, 2023	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
5	Fixing Deprecation of Web Application	Esguerra	Oct 1, 2023	Oct 7, 2023	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
6	Imaging Operating System of Raspberry Pi 4 and Kernel Configuration	Ursora	Oct 8, 2023	Oct 14, 2023	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
7	Implementing Java for Android	Vallente	Oct 15, 2023	Oct 21, 2023	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
8	Integrating Sensors to Raspberry Pi 4	Ursora	Oct 22, 2023	Oct 28, 2023	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
9	Changing Java Implementation to Kotlin	Vallente	Oct 29, 2023	Nov 4, 2023	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
10	Fixing JavaScript to Express Connections	Esguerra	Nov 5, 2023	Nov 11, 2023	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
11	Fixing Kotlin to Firebase Connection	Vallente	Nov 12, 2023	Nov 18, 2023	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
12	Fixing Deprecation of	Ursora	Nov 19, 2023	Nov 25, 2023	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█

designer are also in charge. The fifth and last phase conducts progress and improvements of the entirety of the system and manuscript.

Functional Decomposition Diagram

A functional decomposition diagram (FDD) is a top-down depiction of a function or process in an available FDD. An analyst can use FDD to display business functions and deconstruct them into lower-level procedures and processes.

Figure 5: **Functional Decomposition Diagram (Aquaponic Farmers)**

Figure 5 shows the Functional Decomposition Diagram of AquaFusion's Mobile Monitoring App. The usage of the mobile monitoring app is only exclusive to the farmers and designed for monitoring. This diagram shows three (3) functional components. These are Farmer Account, Farm Management and Monitoring and Customer Support. These functional components are sub-functions describing the manipulation or action a farmer may opt to do in the mobile monitoring app.

The first component, the Farmer Account, comprises the Sign-In and Update Farmer's Account Information sub-functions. First, the Sign-in sub-function allows the authentication of the farmer's account by verifying its legitimacy. Next, the Update Farmer Account's Information sub-function allows updating the farmer's account information. Furthermore, for the Farmer account component, the Request for Farmer Account Registration sub-function allows a farmer to request

an account to access the system through a workgroup which the administrator would later approve. Furthermore, the last component, Farm Management and Monitoring, comprises the View System Notifications, View Sensor Menu, and View Harvest Calendar sub-functions. First, the View Notifications sub-function also allows the farmer to view the system notifications generated from the readings of the IoT device. Next, the View Sensor's Status sub-functions allow the display of the status of the aquatic and terrestrial sensors. Furthermore, lastly, the View Harvest Calendar sub-function allows viewing the farmer's schedules for the harvests. Lastly, for the Customer Support, its sub-functions are Show FAQ and Show Technical Support to provide information on frequent questions or concerns and also to improve customer's experience.

Figure 6: **Functional Decomposition Diagram (Farm Administrator)**

Figure 6 shows the Functional Decomposition Diagram of AquaFusion's Web Administration App. The web administration app is solely exclusive for the farm administrators' use. This diagram shows that this system has four (4) functional components. These are Farm Administrator Account, Farm Workgroup Management, Farm Management and Monitoring and Customer Support. These available components sub-functions describe the manipulation or action a farm administrator may opt to do in the Web Administration App.

The first component, the Farm Administrator Account, comprises the Sign-In and Update admin account information sub-functions. First, the Sign-in sub-function allows for the farm admin's account authentication by verifying its legitimacy. Next, the Update Admin Account's Information sub-function provides for updating the farm administrator's information. This

information includes a farm administrator's profile picture, name, and password. The second component, Farm Workgroup Management, comprises the Add Farmers Account to the Workgroup, Update Farmer Account's Information, and Remove Farmer Accounts from the Workgroup sub-functions. First, the Add Farmers Account to the Workgroup sub-function allows an administrator to add a farmer to the farm's workgroup. Next, the Update Farmer Account's Information enables an administrator to directly change a farmer's account information. And lastly, the Remove Farmer Accounts from the Workgroup sub-function allows an admin to remove a farmer's account from the workgroup in the case of inactivity or an event of resignation from the farm. And the last component, Farm Management and Monitoring, comprises View System Notifications, View Sensor Menu, Manage Harvest Calendar, and Adjust System Thresholds.

First, the View Notifications sub-function allows the farm administrator to view the system notifications generated from the readings of the IoT device. Next, the View Sensor's Status sub-functions will enable the display of the status of the aquatic and terrestrial sensors. Next, the Manage Harvest Calendar sub-function allows the management of schedules for the harvests. Next, the Adjust System Thresholds will enable the farm administrator to adjust the system's thresholds to match the system's configuration. And lastly, the Customer Support and Show FAQ and Technical Support sub-function show the FAQs and Technical Support Information, which the farm's administrator can use to answer technical together with the technical support hotline, which the farm administrator can call when problems occur.

Architectural Layout

The architectural layout shows the overall physical infrastructure of the system. The system is show differently to make it more understandable to the researchers and other beneficiaries.

Figure 7: **Frontal View**

Figure 7 shows the frontal view of the system and describes how it would look in a miniaturized and front perspective. As seen, the figure exposes the entire system and illustrates when the person is looking at it. At the top-left side is the system enclosure, which houses the Raspberry Pi and an ultrasonic sensor which is used in water monitoring, and at the bottom is where the farmer can see the sensor box containing the TDS, pH, and thermometer probe used for measuring the dissolved solids concentration, the pH level, and water temperature can be found at the uppermost top where the ultrasonic sensor for measuring plant growth.

Figure 8: Side View

Figure 8 shows the side view of the system and describes how it would look in a miniaturized and-sided perspective. The figure exposes the entire system and illustrates how the person looks at it from the side.

Figure 9: Top View

Figure 9 shows the top view of the system and describes how it would look in a

miniaturized and whole perspective. The figure exposes the entire system, but the only visible component is the system enclosure box, which describes the system when the person is looking at it at the top.

Figure 10: **Probe Clamp**

Figure 10 shows the probe clamp is a special device designed to fit the holes of the Styrofoam-made repurposed system box that will accommodate the probes that are used in sampling the water quality that passes through. Its diameter is the same as the growing pots used by the system.

Figure 11: **Sensor Box**

Figure 11 shows the sensor box. The sensor box is a rectangular prism-shaped enclosure submerged in the water. The red area offers the place where the sensors are attached.

Side View

Figure 11: **System Enclosure Box**

Figure 11 provides protective and organized housing for the Raspberry Pi and its accompanying components. The box has compact dimensions, measuring 9 inches in length, 5 inches in width, and 6 inches in height. It is constructed from durable and lightweight materials, ensuring the safety of the Raspberry Pi while maintaining its portability. The enclosure box features precise cutouts and openings for easy access to the Raspberry Pi's ports, GPIO pins, and camera module. Additionally, it has built-in ventilation to prevent overheating and ensure optimal performance of the Raspberry Pi. The sleek and modern design of the enclosure box allows it to seamlessly blend into various environments, making it an ideal solution for secure housing and organizing the Raspberry Pi neatly and functionally.

Block Diagram

Figure 13: **Block Diagram**

Figure 13 shows the Block Diagram. Here, the sensors (pH, TDS, Temperature Probe, Ultrasonic, and DHT), the Raspberry Pi Unit, and the relay are interconnected, forming the entire AquaFusion IoT System. The sensors connect through Raspberry Pi's GPIO (General Purpose Input-Output) ports. The ports are assigned to read the values of what the sensors are getting in real-time, which are all read in analog values. Depending on the system's conditions, the logic and algorithm programmed into the Raspberry Pi will automatically direct the relays to drive various electronics and electrical devices to normalize the conditions in the aquaponics system.

Analysis – Design Phase

This phase comprises the use case diagram, user interface diagram, storyboard, database design, entity-relationship diagram, and the system's data dictionary.

Use Case Diagram

The figure below depicts the potential interactions between the AquaFusion system and various types of users.

Figure 14: Use Case Diagram of AquaFusion

Figure 14 shows the use case diagram that comprises two actors: Farm Administrator and Farmers. The Farm Administrator has several abilities, including viewing the FAQ and troubleshooting guide, accessing machine-generated notifications, adjusting system thresholds, and monitoring real-time machine status. The Farm Administrator can also view the Harvest Calendar, edit their account credentials, and log in to their Farm Administrator account. Additionally, they could view the aggregated machine status, set the Harvest Calendar, and register farmers in the system. On the other hand, the Farmers, as the second actor, have similar abilities to the Farm Administrator. They can view the FAQ and troubleshooting guide, access machine-generated notifications, and monitor real-time machine status. Farmers can also log in to their accounts,

consider the Harvest Calendar, and edit their credentials. Overall, this use case diagram outlines the functionalities and interactions between the Farm Administrator and the Farmers in the context of the system.

User Interface Design

This section illustrates the visual representation of the proposed web and mobile application. It showcases how users can engage with the app and highlights its various functionalities.

Figure 15. **Splash Screen Activity**

This figure shows AquaFusion's splash screen. This page appears when farmers launch a mobile application. It serves as the front face of the application. It sets the tone for the user experience and builds anticipation for what lies ahead in the app.

Figure 16. **Login Activity**

This figure shows the login activity. It is the following interface that users encounter after the splash screen. It prompts farmers to enter their email and password for authentication. The system searches for the user's account after supplying the correct credentials and selecting the "Login" button. The farmer is directed to the application's dashboard if the account is present. However, if the credentials are incorrect, the farmer remains on the same interface and has two additional options: registering for an account or resetting a forgotten password.

The image shows a registration form on a dark blue background. At the top, there is a logo of a stylized plant with two branches. Below the logo, the text reads: "Register to monitor and optimize crop cultivation and crucial ambient conditions for your aquaponics farm's success." The form consists of five input fields, each with a label and an icon: "Workgroup ID" (people icon), "Full Name" (person icon), "Email Address" (envelope icon), "Password" (lock icon), and "Confirm Password" (lock icon). To the right of the password and confirm password fields, there are eye icons to toggle visibility. At the bottom, there is a green "REGISTER" button and a link that says "Existing User? Login".

Figure 17. **Register Activity**

This figure shows the registration activity. This is where farmers are required to register and await approval from farmer administrators. During registration, they must provide essential information, including their workgroup identification, full name, email address, password, and password confirmation. The registration process begins when they click the "Register" button. Once the farmer submits the required credentials, their account details are stored in the system, but they cannot log in immediately. Instead, farmer administrators review and approve these registrations, ensuring that only authorized individuals gain access to the application. Once approved, farmers will be able to log in and access the application's features.

**FORGOT
PASSWORD?**

Provide your account's email for which you want to reset your password.

Email Address

CONTINUE

Figure 18. **Forgot Password Activity**

This figure shows the forgot password activity. This activity appears when farmers opt to reset their forgotten password. Farmers enter their email addresses to initiate the password reset process. If the email is in the database, the farmer would receive an email containing instructions on how to reset their password.

Figure 19. **Reset Password Activity**

This figure shows the reset password activity, which prompts farmers to reset their password. This activity is initiated when a farmer has successfully requested to reset their password. Once the user has successfully entered and saved their new password, their account's password will be updated, and farmers will be able to log in with their new credentials.

Figure 20. **Sensor Menu Activity**

This figure shows the sensor menu. This interface allows users to view real-time data related to aquatic and terrestrial parameters in their aquaponics system. It visualizes essential metrics such as pH levels, water temperature, TDS (Total Dissolved Liquids), water level, humidity, and air temperature. Farmers can monitor the current values, view sensor details and system thresholds, track trends over time, and receive alerts if any parameters deviate from the desired range.

Figure 21. **Sensor Status Activity**

This figure shows the sensor status activity. This activity provides a quick and convenient overview of the status of various sensors in the aquaponics system. This activity focuses on indicating whether the sensors are functioning correctly and operational.

Figure 22. Sensor Data Graph Activity

This figure shows the sensor data graph activity. It displays a comprehensive graphical representation of sensor data collected from the aquaponics system. Farmers can explore the graphs that depict the variations in water pH levels, water temperature, water turbidity, water level, humidity, and air temperature over a selected period. It allows farmers to analyze historical trends, identify patterns, and make informed decisions regarding system management.

Figure 23. **Plant Growth Monitoring Activity**

This figure shows the plant growth monitoring screen. It displays the growth progress of plants in the aquaponics system through visual representation. It provides an overview of the plant growth by height over a selected period, allowing users to gain valuable insights into their plants' overall progress and health.

Figure 24. **Harvest Calendar Activity**

This figure shows the harvest calendar activity. This activity provides farmers with a concise and organized view of crucial harvest details in the aquaponics system. It includes information such as the date planted for a batch of plants, the scheduled harvest date, harvest name, and a brief harvest description. Farmers can easily grasp the date range from planting to harvest, allowing for effective management of their farming tasks and ensuring timely and successful harvests.

Figure 25. **Notifications Activity**

This figure shows the notifications activity. It consolidates all system alerts and notifications in one place. Farmers can review essential updates, such as changes in aquatic and terrestrial parameters or system maintenance notifications. This activity ensures that farmers stay informed about critical events and can take appropriate actions to maintain the optimal operation of their aquaponics system.

Figure 26. **Profile Activity**

This figure shows the profile activity. It provides farmers with comprehensive information about their accounts and facilitates efficient management of profile settings. The screen prominently showcases the user's workgroup identification, email address, and profile image, creating a personalized and visually appealing interface. To enable users to update their profile information, two primary buttons, namely "Edit Profile" and "Change Password," are provided within the activity. Additionally, users can access support and information about the application through the "Help & About Application" button. Moreover, a logout button is included in the activity, ensuring farmers can securely log out of their AquaFusion account. The farmer's session is terminated upon clicking this button, safeguarding their privacy and preventing unauthorized access.

Figure 27. **Edit Profile Activity**

This figure shows the edit profile activity. It allows farmers to modify their account information, such as updating profile images and their names. The activity includes an option to upload a new image, allowing farmers to select a personalized profile picture that best represents them. Farmers can choose an image from their device's gallery and set it as their profile picture. Moreover, farmers can modify their names by typing in the new name they want. The activity offers a straightforward text input field that allows farmers to update their names as desired. Farmers can tap the "Save Changes" button to save the changes made to their profile. It ensures the updated profile information is recorded and applied to their AquaFusion account.

Figure 28. **Verify Farmer Account Activity**

This figure shows the verify farmer account activity. It appears when farmers opt to change their password. It serves as a security measure by asking users to enter their current password for verification. This step ensures that only authorized users can change their account credentials. The activity includes a secure text input field that masks the characters as farmers type in their password to protect sensitive information. This feature enhances account security and ensures that the rightful account owner in AquaFusion makes password changes.

**CHANGE
PASSWORD**

Your identity has been verified! Set your new password.

New Password

Confirm New Password

Save Changes

Cancel

Figure 29. **Change Password Activity**

After successful authorization to change their password, AquaFusion displays the Change Password Activity. In this activity, farmers can securely set a new password for their account. The activity includes masked text input fields to keep the new password confidential and ensure a strong and unique password creation process.

Figure 30. **Help and About Application Activity**

This figure shows the help and application activity. It provides farmers with brief information about the application and its development team.

Figure 31. Technical Support Activity

This figure shows the technical support activity. This activity gives farmers access to frequently asked questions and corresponding answers to assist with common queries and troubleshooting.

Figure 32. **Web Administration App Login Screen**

This figure shows the login screen of web administration. What differs with this with the mobile app is that access to this login screen is to the administrators of the devices. Here, the administrators can enter their credentials to login into their accounts.

Figure 33. **Web Administration App Forgotten Password Screen**

This figure shows the administration web app forgotten password screen. It is where farm administrators can search their accounts if they need to remember their passwords.

Figure 34. **Web Administration App Account Not Found Screen**

This figure shows the administration web app account not found screen. This screen only appears when the farm administrator's account is not on the database since it will be cross-matched.

Figure 35. **Web Administration App Enter New Password Screen**

This figure shows the administration web app's new password screen. It is where farm administrators can enter their new passwords.

Figure 36. Web Administration App Dashboard Panel

This figure shows the Dashboard Panel. The dashboard displays a portion of the notifications together with others like water status, plant growth, etc. This panel shows a quick overview of the system's status like the system's latest notifications, water temperature, air temperature, and air humidity for the day.

The screenshot shows the 'Manage Workgroup' panel in the AquaFusion web administration app. The panel displays a table of workgroup members with the following columns: Account ID, Name, Email Address, and Delete Account. The table lists six members, each with a 'DELETE ACCOUNT' button.

Account ID	Name	Email Address	Delete Account
g4939492971123778484001	Jurender Unora T	tdqmeder.professional@gmail.com	DELETE ACCOUNT
79d6749912781123778484001	Jurender Unora T	tdqmeder@yahoo.com	DELETE ACCOUNT
JAC811943044408123778484001	Harshad	shreshth.agney.90@gmail.com	DELETE ACCOUNT
1032492_774934303_C401421421	Jarene Caroline Solente	jaronecaroline@gmail.com	DELETE ACCOUNT
g4939492971123778484001	Ernesto Park	erose@aquafusion.com	DELETE ACCOUNT
1032492_774934303_C401421421	System Tech	system@aquafusion.com	DELETE ACCOUNT
1032492_774934303_C401421421	Harshad	shreshth.agney.90@gmail.com	DELETE ACCOUNT

Figure 37. Web Administration App Manage Workgroup Panel

This figure shows the Team Management Panel. This panel allows administrators to view and delete the farmers within the workgroup as displayed in the table.

Figure 38. Web Administration App Register Farmer Panel

This figure shows the Registration Panel. This panel allows for the direct registration of a farmer account for a farmer by a farm administrator for them to access the system. By clicking the approve farmer request button, the farm administrator can view the registration requests made by the farmers who want to join the workgroup.

Figure 39. Web Administration App Approve Farmer Registration Panel

This figure shows the continuation of the registration Panel. This panel allows the approval of the registration of a farmer account by a farm administrator for them to access the system. This panel shows when the farm administrator clicks the button below the Register Farmer Panel.

Figure 40. Web Administration App Harvest Calendar Panel

This figure shows the Harvest Calendar Panel. It is where administrators can set the harvest and plant date of the crops in the system. By clicking the calendar, the farm administrator will be presented with a modal that allows them to select the dates and set the information for a specific harvest.

Figure 41. Web Administration App Notifications Panel

This figure shows the Notifications Panel. It is where the system notifications and logs, depending on the date, are placed and shown to farm administrators. The farm administrators can also download the backlogs of the system given a specific range of date.

Figure 42. Web Administration App Aquatic Sensor Status Panel

This figure shows the Aquatic Sensor Status Panel. It is where the statistics and a graphical representation of the data that the sensors had gathered in a day for the use in monitoring the water are viewed and shown. Graphs show the water volume, pH level, water turbidity, and water temperature. In addition, the farm administrator can also opt to download the backlogs of the sensors here.

Figure 43. Web Administration App Terrestrial Sensor Status Panel

This figure shows the Terrestrial Sensor Status Panel. It is where the statistics and a graphical representation of the data that the sensors had gathered in a day for the use in monitoring the air are viewed and shown. Graphs show the air humidity, temperature, and plant growth meter depending on a specific period. In addition, the farm administrator can also opt to download the backlogs of the sensors here.

Figure 44. **Web Administration App Threshold Adjustment Panel**

This figure shows the Threshold Adjustment Panel. It is where the farm administrator can adjust the system's threshold levels for different sensors depending on the farm's setup.

Figure 45. **Web Administration App FAQ and Technical Support Panel**

This figure shows the Technical Support Panel. The FAQ, documentation, and contacts regarding technical support for the IoT device are displayed here. This panel provides detailed instructions for administrators to follow in maintaining and troubleshooting the system in cases where proper system maintenance and issues and problems arise, which requires solving the situation simultaneously.

Figure 46. Web Administration App About Panel

This figure shows the About Panel. It is where the application's version with its developers is present.

Figure 47. Web Administration App Profile Panel

This figure shows the Profile Panel. It is where the administrator can edit their account information, like their name and passwords, in case they've forgotten it.

Storyboard

The storyboard presents the user experience sequentially, showcasing the logical flow of the entire system through visual representations of the user interfaces. It begins with the first UI and continues until the final interface.

Figure 48. **Storyboard of Mobile Monitoring Application**

This figure shows the storyboard of the mobile monitoring application for aquaponic farmers and practitioners. Upon launching the application, farmers are greeted with an engaging and visually appealing splash screen, introducing them to the aquaponics monitoring experience. After the splash screen, the application seamlessly transitions to the login page. Farmers can log in to their existing accounts using their registered credentials. The login page also offers a user-friendly registration process for those who still need to be registered with a workgroup identification. Once logged in, farmers gain access to the dashboard, where farmers can view real-time sensor readings and monitor plant growth.

The dashboard provides a comprehensive overview of critical data for effective aquaponics management. Additionally, farmers can access the harvest calendar, enabling them to track their harvesting schedule efficiently. Notifications are displayed in a designated window, informing farmers of essential events or system updates. This feature helps farmers stay on top of their aquaponics system's performance and promptly respond to alerts. The profile activity window allows farmers to personalize their accounts by modifying their names and pictures. This customization fosters a sense of identity within the application and enhances user engagement. Furthermore, the application facilitates password change for added security. It empowers farmers to update their credentials whenever necessary, ensuring the safety of accounts. The application includes a section that provides information about the application itself and a list of frequently asked questions (FAQs) to assist farmers. This resourceful feature addresses common queries and aids users in navigating the application effectively.

The storyboard embodies AquaFusion's commitment to empowering aquaponic farmers and practitioners with an intuitive and feature-rich mobile monitoring application. AquaFusion aims to revolutionize intelligent farming practices and foster sustainable agricultural management by combining data-driven insights, customization options, and helpful resources. The continuous development and user-centric approach ensure AquaFusion remains the go-to solution for aquaponics enthusiasts seeking optimal productivity and growth in their farming endeavors.

Figure 49. **Storyboard of Web Monitoring Application**

The program workflow for the web management application starts from the login page. The login page is responsible for authenticating the entered credentials of a farm administrator. A farm administrator must register through the hotline's aid if the administrator needs writing. If the farm administrator forgets the password, it will prompt the administrator to enter the workgroup name together with their username. Once the account is found, the farm administrator can elect a new password with its confirmation, which the administrator may use to log in. Once logged in, the Farm Administrator is in the application's dashboard, which shows brief information from the system. From anywhere in the system besides the About page, which is only accessible through the Help and About page, the Farm Administrator may access any pages indexed from the top and sidebar. First, the sidebar has three (3) sections: Users, System, and Session. In the Users section, there are three (3) subsections: Manage Workgroup, Register Farmer, and Harvest Calendar. Next, the System section has four (5) areas: System Notifications, Aquatic Sensors Status, Terrestrial Sensors Status, Adjust System Thresholds, and Help and About subsections. And, lastly in the session section is where the logout subsection is. When clicked, it would automatically redirect the user back to the login page and erase their credentials, prompting them to re-enter before getting back into the system.

Database Design

The database design is a compilation of the database's detailed data model. The data model's logical inter-relationship options, physical design options, and material storage characteristics are required to produce a design in a data definition language.

Entity Relationship Diagram

The entity relationship diagram visualizes the relationships between entities like people, things, or concepts in a database. It can define the entities and their attributes, show the relationships between them, and illustrate the logical structure of databases.

Figure 50: **Entity Relationship Diagram (Aquaponic Farmers)**

Figure 50 represents the relationship between the user and other entities. The figure shows how foreign keys connect to the tables and how the data are in the different tables. The entity user is interdependent with other entities.

Figure 51: **Entity Relationship Diagram (Farm Administrator)**

Figure 51 represents the administrator's relationship with the user. The figure shows how the registered user appears in the admin table.

Data Dictionary

This sector contains an overview of each table in the database, showing the Table Name, Attribute Name, Contents, Type, PK or FK, and FK Referenced Table.

Table 6
REGISTER

TABLE NAME	ATTRIBUTE NAME	CONTENTS	TYPE	PK OR FK	FK REFERENCED TABLE
register	email	User's registered email	VARCHAR(255)	PK	
	workgroupId	User's assigned workgroup	VARCHAR(255)	FK	workgroup
	fullName	User's registered full name	VARCHAR(255)		
	password	User's registered password	VARCHAR(255)		

Overview of table 6, the register table. The records stored by these fields are the information for each registered farmer in their profile and other activities.

Table 7
FORGOT PASSWORD

forgotPassword	emailAddress	User's registered email	VARCHAR(255)	FK	register
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Overview of table 7, forgotPassword table. It will be needed to reset the account's password.

Table 8
CONFIRM PASSWORD

confirmPassword	emailAddress	User's registered email	VARCHAR(255)	FK	register
	password	User's changed password	VARCHAR(255)	FK	register

Overview of table 8, confirmPassword table. It will be necessary to reference the email to reset the account's new password.

Table 9
LOGIN

login	emailAddress	User's registered email	VARCHAR(255)	FK	register
	password	User's registered password	VARCHAR(255)	FK	register

Overview of table 9, login table. It consists of emailAddress and password. The record will be retrieved and used to login into the application and unique identifiers for each user.

Table 10
PROFILE

profile	accountId	User's profile identification	INT	PK	
	workgroupId	User's assigned workgroup	VARCHAR(255)	FK	workgroup
	emailAddress	User's registered email	VARCHAR(255)	FK	register
	fullName	User's registered full name	VARCHAR(255)		
	headerImage	User's profile image	VARCHAR(255)		

Overview of table 10, the profile table. It consists of accountId, workgroupId, emailAddress, fullName, and headerImage. It will be needed to display the user's email and full name and its corresponding picture stored as the file path or URL of the image.

Table 11
PROFILE ACTIVITY

profileActivity	activityId	User's unique activity identification	INT	PK	
	accountId	User's profile identification	INT	FK	profile
	fullName	User's registered full name	VARCHAR(255)		
	headerImage	User's profile image	VARCHAR(255)		

Overview of table 11, the profileActivity table. It consists of activityId, accountId, fullName, and headerImage. It will be needed to input the user's full name and corresponding picture stored as the file path or URL of the image.

Table 12
CHANGE PASSWORD VERIFICATION

changePassVerif	accountId	User's profile identification	INT	FK	profile
	emailAddress	User's registered email	VARCHAR(255)	FK	register
	password	User's registered password	VARCHAR(255)		

Overview of table 12, the changePassVerif. It consists of accountId, emailAddress, and password. It will be needed to verify the user's password that corresponds to the user's registered email.

Table 13
INPUT NEW PASSWORD

inputNewPass	accountId	User's profile identification	INT	FK	profile
	emailAddress	User's registered email	VARCHAR(255)	FK	register
	password	User's registered password	VARCHAR(255)		

Overview of table 13, the inputNewPass. It consists of accountId, emailAddress, and password. It will be necessary to input the user's new password corresponding to the user's registered email.

Table 14
PLANT GROWTH MONITORING

plantGrowth	growthId	Plant growth identification number	INT	PK	
	userId	User's profile identification	INT	FK	profile
	avgGrowthRate	Plant's average growth rate	FLOAT		
	workgroupId	User's assigned workgroup	VARCHAR(255)	FK	workgroup

Overview of table 14, the plantGrowth table. It consists of growthId, userId, avgGrowthRate, and workgroupId. It retrieves a numerical, alphabetical, and graphical representation of plant growth.

Table 15

SENSOR

sensor	sensorId	Sensor's identification	INT	PK	
	name	Sensor's name	VARCHAR(255)		
	calibration	Sensor's calibration	VARCHAR(255)		
	timestamp	Notification date and time	TIMESTAMP		
	sensortypeId	Type of sensor identification	INT	FK	sensorType
	workgroupId	User's assigned workgroup	VARCHAR(255)	FK	workgroup

Overview of table 15, the sensor table. It consists of sensorId, name, calibration, and sensortypeId. The records retrieve to classify the unique identification number of the sensor, calibration, and name.

Table 16

SENSOR TYPE

sensorType	sensortypeId	Type of sensor identification	INT	PK	
	type	Sensor type classification	VARCHAR(255)		
	description	Sensor type description	VARCHAR(255)		
	workgroupId	User's assigned workgroup	VARCHAR(255)	FK	workgroup

Overview of table 16, the sensorType table. It consists of sensortypeId, type, and description—the retrieved records to classify the unique identification number of the kind of sensor used.

Table 17
SENSOR STATUS

sensorStatus	sensortypeId	Type of sensor identification	INT	PK	
	sensorId	Sensor type classification	INT	FK	sensor
	status	Sensor type description	BOOLEAN		

Overview of table 17, the sensor status table. It consists of sensortypeId, type, and description. The retrieved records to classify the status of the sensor.

Table 18
SENSOR GRAPH

sensorGraph	sensorGraphId	Graph of sensor identification	INT	PK	
	sensorId	Sensor type classification	INT	FK	sensor
	graphData	Sensors graphed data	INTs		

Overview of table 18, the sensorGraph table. It consists of sensorGraphId, sensorId, and graphData. The records that are retrieved display the graphed data of the sensors instead of displaying numerical values.

Table 19
SENSOR VALUES

sensorValues	sensorValuesId	Graph of sensor identification	INT	PK	
	sensorId	Sensor type classification	INT	FK	sensor
	sensorData	Sensors displayed data	INT		

Overview of table 19, the sensorGraph table. It consists of sensorGraphId, sensorId, and graphData. The records that are retrieved display the graphed data of the sensors instead of displaying numerical values.

Table 20
SENSOR MENU

sensorMenu	sensorMenuId	Notification system identification number	INT	PK	
	accountId	User's profile identification	INT	FK	profile
	sensorId	Sensor's identification	INT	FK	sensor
	sensorTypeId	Type of sensor	INT	FK	sensorType

Overview of table 20, the sensorMenu table. It consists of sensorMenuId, accountId, sensorId and, sensorTypeId. The record displays the list of sensors and their corresponding values.

Table 21
NOTIFICATIONS

notification	notificationId	Notification system identification number	INT	PK	
	sensorMenuId	Notification system identification number	INT	FK	sensorMenu
	notificationType	Sensor threshold	INT		
	notificationMessage	Notification message displayed	INT		
	timestamp	Notification date and time	TIMESTAMP		
	workgroupId	User's assigned workgroup	VARCHAR(255)	FK	workgroup

Overview of table 21, the notifications table. It consists of notificationId, sensorMenuId, notificationType, notificationMessage, timestamp, and workgroupId. The records retrieved the notifications and alerts of the application on all monitoring pages.

Table 22
HARVEST CALENDAR

harvestCalendar	harvestId	Harvest identification number	INT	PK	
	harvestDate	Harvest date schedule	DATE		
	harvestDescription	Harvest general description	VARCHAR(255)		
	workgroupId	User's assigned workgroup	VARCHAR(255)	FK	workgroup

Overview of table 22, the harvest calendar table. It consists of harvestId, harvestDate, harvestDescription, and workgroupId. The records retrieved here will reference the harvest schedule and its description that the user can view.

Table 23
LOGIN ADMINISTRATOR

loginAdmin	emailAddress	Administrator's registered email	VARCHAR(255)	PK	
	password	Administrator's registered password	VARCHAR(255)		

Overview of table 23, the loginAdmin table. It consists of emailAddress and password. The records are retrieved to login into the application as an administrator.

Table 24
ADMINISTRATOR USER LINK

adminUserLink	adminId	Administrator's profile identification	INT	FK	profile
	workgroupId	User's profile identification	INT	FK	workgroup

Overview of table 24, the adminUserLink table. It consists of adminId and userId. The record connects administrators with their associated users as a junction or associative table.

Table 25
PROFILE ADMINISTRATOR

adminProfile	adminId	Administrator's profile identification	INT	PK	
	workgroupId	Administrator's assigned workgroup	VARCHAR(255)	FK	workgroup
	emailAddress	Administrator's registered email	VARCHAR(255)	FK	register
	fullName	Administrator's registered full name	VARCHAR(255)		
	adminImage	Administrator's profile image	VARCHAR(255)		

Overview of table 25, the profile table. It consists of adminId, workgroupId, emailAddress, fullName and, adminImage. The record displays the administrator's email and full name and its corresponding picture stored as the file path or URL of the image.

Table 26
ADMINISTRATOR REGISTER

TABLE NAME	ATTRIBUTE NAME	CONTENTS	TYPE	PK OR FK	FK REFERENCED TABLE
register	email	User's registered email	VARCHAR(255)	PK	
	workgroupId	User's assigned workgroup	VARCHAR(255)	FK	workgroup
	fullName	User's registered full name	VARCHAR(255)		

Overview of table 26, the administrator register table. The records stored by these fields are the information for each farm administrator in their profile and other activities.

Network Design

This section includes the planning and implementation of computer networks and infrastructure. It comprises evaluating, analyzing, and sizing the network—a network diagram representing the overall network architecture as a roadmap for physically assembling the network.

Network Model

The AquaFusion application has three users in the database: the aquaponic farmer, the Administrator, and the super Administrator. Aquaponic farmers register with the Administrator; the aquaponic farmer will input their details and credentials. The Administrator will save their credential and supervise the aquaponic farmer already registered. The super Administrator will oversee all the users, including the Administrator, on all their credentials and subscriptions.

Figure 52: **Network Models**

Figure 52 states that aquaponic farmers register with the Administrator. The aquaponic farmer will input their details and credentials. The Administrator will save their credential and supervise the aquaponic farmer already registered. The super Administrator will oversee all the users, including the Administrator, on all their credentials and subscriptions.

Network Topology

The AquaFusion application is an IoT-based that can be accessed from the Raspberry Pi 4 through mobile and web application and can be accessed either on WiFi or with cellular data.

Figure 53: Network Topology

Figure 53 shows the AquaFusion network topology; smartphones must have access to the Internet either from Wi-Fi or cellular data. The Raspberry Pi 4 will be connected to the Internet from Wi-Fi or cellular data and is responsible for sending data to the cloud. The application on the smartphone will send requests and details to the Administrator. The Administrator will be the one who will manage the users' details and credentials and read all the information from the AquaFusion database to display in the application. At the same time, the Super Administrator will oversee all the Administrators enlisted on the application and the users that the respective Administrators manage.

Development/Construction/Build Phase

This section marks the start of the project's implementation. It includes the techniques needed to finish the system and the system's functionalities broken down into modules that will guide the execution phase. It also consists of the project's software and hardware specification, and this phase's output will serve as input in the implementation process.

Technology Stack Diagram

The technology stack diagram depicts the requirements required to complete the proposed architecture. It separates the technologies necessary, whether in the development of the mobile application, web applications, hardware development, or future enhancement.

ANDROID DEVELOPMENT	IOT DEVELOPMENT	WEB DEVELOPMENT
Kotlin	Python3	React (JavaScript)
Android Studio	Ubuntu Raspberry Pi 22.04	Material UI Design
Android SDK	Raspberry Pi 4 TP-Link Archer T2U WiFi Adapter Module	Express (TypeScript) Node.js
CLOUD SERVICES		CLOUD SERVICES
Firestore Authentication GitHub	Ultrasonic Distance Sensor DHT22 Temperature and Humidity Sensor Module DS18B20 Water Temperature Sensor Analog TDS Sensor Module PH-4502C Liquid pH Sensor ADS1115 Digital to Analog Converter Chip Temperature Sensor I2C Liquid Crystal Display TCA9548A 8 – Channel I2C Multiplexer Chip	GoDaddy Hostman Firebase Cloud Functions Firebase Admin SDK Firebase Authentication Github
SERVER		
Firebase Storage Firebase Realtime Database Firebase Firestore		

Figure 54: **Technology Stack Diagram**

The researchers employ the Internet of Things, alongside various technologies and programming languages, to create mobile and web applications, integrating the Raspberry Pi 4. For Android app development, the researchers use the Android Software Development Kit, while for web apps, React and Material UI Design is chosen. The mobile application's front-end and back-

end are powered by Kotlin, chosen for its rich library collection, APIs, and emulators, along with strong community support. Conversely, the web application is developed using JavaScript for the front-end React Application and TypeScript for the Express back-end Application. GoDaddy serves as the domain provider, and the front-end application is deployed via Hostman. Both the mobile and web applications use GitHub for repository management and extensively utilize Firebase for their functionalities. The functionalities range from cloud data storage, databases, and cloud functions.

Program Specification

The program specification is the information gathered and incorporated into procedures, including the proposed systems needed and expected outputs. It also specifies the module each team member should work on.

Table 27
LIST OF MODULES

Programmers	Modules	Farmers	Farm Administrators
Janine Christine Vallente	Farmer Account Management (Mobile)		
	1. Sign-In	*	
	2. Register	*	
	3. Forgot and Reset Password	*	
	4. Update Farm Account Information	*	
	No. of Points	1	
Janine Christine Vallente Junester Ursora II	Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)		
	1. View System Notifications	*	
	2. View Sensor Menu	*	
	3. View Harvest Calendar	*	
	No. of Points	1	

Table 27.1
LIST OF MODULES CONT'D

Janine Christine Vallente	Customer Support (Mobile)		
	1. Show FAQ	*	
	2. Show Technical Support	*	
	No. of Points	1	
Elijah Nicholas Esguerra	Farmer Administrator Account Management (Web)		
	1. Sign-In		*
	2. Register		*
	3. Forgot and Reset Password		*
	4. Update Farm Administrator		*
	No. of Points		1
Elijah Nicholas Esguerra	Farm Workgroup Management (Web)		*
	1. Add Farmer Account to Workgroup		*
	2. Update Farmer Account from Workgroup		*
	3. Remove Farmer Account from Workgroup		*
	4. View Farmer Information		*
	No. of Points		1
Elijah Nicholas Esguerra Junester Ursora II	Farm Management and Monitoring (Web)		
	1. Adjust System Thresholds		*
	2. View System Notifications		*
	3. View Sensor Menu		*
	4. Manage Harvest Calendar		*
	No. of Points		1

Table 27.2
LIST OF MODULES CONT'D

Elijah Nicholas Esguerra	Customer Support (Web)		
	1. Show FAQ		*
	2. Show Technical Support		*
	No. of Points		1
Number of Modules per User		3	4
Total Number of Modules		7	

Testing/Quality Assurance Phase

This section exhibits the different testing levels utilized by the proponents to test the mobile application. It comprises the unit, integration, alpha and acceptance testing.

Unit Testing

Unit testing is a level of software testing where individual units/components of the software are tested. It is also called component testing where the testing is done in every module. The purpose is to validate that each unit of the software performs as designed.

Table 28
UNIT TESTING – AQUAPONIC FARMER

Module Name	Unit Name	Date Tested	Test Case ID	Test Case Description	Expected Results	Actual Results	Remarks
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Register	12/4/23	F1	Missing Fields	Error Message Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Register	12/4/23	F2	Invalid Email Address	Error Message Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Register	12/4/23	F3	Password is less than 6 characters	Error Message Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed

Table 28.1

UNIT TESTING – AQUAPONIC FARMER

Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Register	12/4/23	F4	Password and Confirm Password does not match	Error Message Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Register	12/4/23	F5	Email Address already exists	Error Message Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Register	12/4/23	F6	Valid User Input Credentials	Farmer Account waiting for account approval	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Sign-In	12/4/23	F7	Missing Fields	Error Message Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Sign-In	12/4/23	F8	Unregistered Farmer account	Error Message Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Sign-In	12/4/23	F9	Unverified Farmer account	Error Message Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Sign-In	12/4/23	F10	Invalid Email Address	Error Message Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Sign-In	12/4/23	F11	Invalid Login Credential	Error Message Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Sign-In	12/4/23	F12	Valid Email Address and Password	Successful Login (Directed Sensor Menu)	Performed as expected	Passed

Table 28.2

UNIT TESTING – AQUAPONIC FARMER

Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Forgot and Reset Password	12/4/23	F13	Unregistered Email Address	Error Message Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Forgot and Reset Password	12/4/23	F14	Invalid Email Address	Error Message Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Forgot and Reset Password	12/4/23	F15	Valid Email Address	Password Reset Email Sent	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Forgot and Reset Password	12/4/23	F16	Missing Fields	Error Message Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Forgot and Reset Password	12/4/23	F17	Password is less than 6 characters	Error Message Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Forgot and Reset Password	12/4/23	F18	Valid New Password Input	Successful Password Reset	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Update Farm Account's Information	12/4/23	F19	Press Upload Image Button	Photo gallery can be accessed	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Update Farm Account's Information	12/4/23	F20	Chose New Picture in gallery	New Picture Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed

Table 28.3

UNIT TESTING – AQUAPONIC FARMER

Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Update Farm Account 's Information	12/4/23	F21	Saved New Profile Picture in Edit Profile	New Picture Saved	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Update Farm Account 's Information	12/4/23	F22	Edit New Name	New Name Saved	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Update Farm Account 's Information	12/4/23	F23	Upload New Profile Picture and Edit New Name at the same time	New Profile Picture and New Name Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Update Farm Account 's Information	12/4/23	F24	Missing Fields in Edit Profile	Error Message Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Update Farm Account 's Information	12/4/23	F25	Cancel Edit Profile	Edit Profile cancelled (Navigated back to Profile Fragment)	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Update Farm Account 's Information	12/4/23	F26	Input current password for account verification	Setting new password permitted (Directed to Change Password Activity)	Performed as expected	Passed

Table 28.4

UNIT TESTING – AQUAPONIC FARMER

Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Update Farm Account's Information	12/4/23	F27	Input incorrect current password for account verification	Error Message Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Update Farm Account's Information	12/4/23	F28	Missing Fields in Account Verification	Error Message Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Update Farm Account's Information	12/4/23	F29	Missing Fields in Change Password Activity	Error Message Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Update Farm Account's Information	12/4/23	F30	New Password and Confirm New Password doesn't match	Error Message Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Update Farm Account's Information	12/4/23	F31	New Password is less than 6 characters	Error Message Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed
Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Update Farm Account's Information	12/4/23	F32	New Password and Confirm Password matches	Password updated successfully	Performed as expected	Passed

Table 28.5

UNIT TESTING – AQUAPONIC FARMER

Farmer Account Management (Mobile)	Update Farm Account's Information	12/4/23	F33	Cancellation of Changing Password	Changing password cancelled (Navigated back to Profile Fragment)	Performed as expected	Passed
Customer Support (Mobile)	Show FAQ	12/4/23	F34	View FAQ	FAQ Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed
Customer Support (Mobile)	Show Technical Support	12/4/23	F35	View Technical Support	Technical Support Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Harvest Calendar	12/4/23	F36	Press Harvest Calendar Icon	Harvest Details Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Harvest Calendar	12/4/23	F37	Press View Harvest Calendar Button	Date Planted and Harvest Date Range in Calendar is Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Harvest Calendar	12/4/23	F38	Press View Harvest Calendar Button	Date Planted and Harvest Date Range in Calendar is Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	Sensor Menu	12/4/23	F39	View Sensor Data Numerical Values	Sensor Numerical Values Displayed	Performed as expected	Passed

Table 28.6

UNIT TESTING – AQUAPONIC FARMER

Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	Sensor Menu	12/4/23	F40	Press View Sensor Status Link	Sensor Statuses Displayed (Directed to Sensor Status Activity)	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	Sensor Menu	12/4/23	F41	Press Back to Sensor Menu Button from Sensor Status	Navigated back to Sensor Menu Fragment	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	Sensor Menu	12/4/23	F42	Enable Push Notifications in Notifications Fragment	Navigated to application settings for permissions	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	Sensor Menu	12/4/23	F43	Disable Push Notifications in Notifications Fragment	Navigated to application settings for permissions	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F44	Display Sensor Status in Sensor Status Activity	Display Sensor Readings	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F45	Trigger pH Sensor Status On	pH Sensor Card will change color to green	Performed as expected	Passed

Table 28.7

UNIT TESTING – AQUAPONIC FARMER

Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F46	Trigger pH Sensor Status Off	pH Sensor Card will change color to red	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F47	Trigger TDS Sensor Status On	pH Sensor Card will change color to green	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F48	Trigger TDS Sensor Status Off	pH Sensor Card will change color to red	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F49	Trigger DHT Sensor Status On	pH Sensor Card will change color to green	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F50	Trigger DHT Sensor Status Off	pH Sensor Card will change color to red	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F51	Trigger Water Temperature Sensor Status On	pH Sensor Card will change color to green	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F52	Trigger Water Temperature Sensor Status Off	pH Sensor Card will change color to red	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F53	Trigger Ultrasonic Water Sensor Status On	pH Sensor Card will change color to green	Performed as expected	Passed

Table 28.8

UNIT TESTING – AQUAPONIC FARMER

Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F54	Trigger Ultrasonic Water Sensor Status Off	pH Sensor Card will change color to red	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F55	Trigger Ultrasonic Plant Sensor Status On	pH Sensor Card will change color to green	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F56	Trigger Ultrasonic Plant Sensor Status Off	pH Sensor Card will change color to red	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F57	Display Sensor Status in Sensor Status Activity	Display Sensor Readings	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F58	Trigger pH Sensor Status On	pH Sensor Card will change color to green	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F59	Trigger pH Sensor Status Off	pH Sensor Card will change color to red	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F60	Trigger TDS Sensor Status On	pH Sensor Card will change color to green	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F61	Trigger TDS Sensor Status Off	pH Sensor Card will change color to red	Performed as expected	Passed

Table 28.9

UNIT TESTING – AQUAPONIC FARMER

Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F62	Trigger DHT Sensor Status On	pH Sensor Card will change color to green	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F63	Trigger DHT Sensor Status Off	pH Sensor Card will change color to red	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F64	Trigger Water Temperature Sensor Status On	pH Sensor Card will change color to green	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F65	Trigger Water Temperature Sensor Status Off	pH Sensor Card will change color to red	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F66	Trigger Ultrasonic Water Sensor Status On	pH Sensor Card will change color to green	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F67	Trigger Ultrasonic Water Sensor Status Off	pH Sensor Card will change color to red	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F68	Trigger Ultrasonic Plant Sensor Status On	pH Sensor Card will change color to green	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View Sensor Menu	12/6/23	F69	Trigger Ultrasonic Plant Sensor Status Off	pH Sensor Card will change color to red	Performed as expected	Passed

Table 28.10

UNIT TESTING – AQUAPONIC FARMER

Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F70	Notify pH Level High Threshold	Display Notifications in Notification Fragment	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F71	Notify pH Level Low Threshold	Display Notifications in Notification Fragment	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F72	Notify pH Sensor Status Off	Display Notifications in Notification Fragment	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F73	Notify TDS Level High Threshold	Display Notifications in Notification Fragment	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F74	Notify TDS Level Low Threshold	Display Notifications in Notification Fragment	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F75	Notify TDS Sensor Status Off	Display Notifications in Notification Fragment	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F76	Notify Water Temperature High Threshold	Display Notifications in Notification Fragment	Performed as expected	Passed

Table 28.11

UNIT TESTING – AQUAPONIC FARMER

Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F77	Notify Water Temperature Low Threshold	Display Notifications in Notification Fragment	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F78	Notify Water Temperature Sensor Status Off	Display Notifications in Notification Fragment	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F79	Notify Water Level High Threshold	Display Notifications in Notification Fragment	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F80	Notify Water Level Low Threshold	Display Notifications in Notification Fragment	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F81	Notify Ultrasonic Water Sensor Status Off	Display Notifications in Notification Fragment	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F81	Notify Air Temperature High Threshold	Display Notifications in Notification Fragment	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F82	Notify Air Temperature Low Threshold	Display Notifications in Notification Fragment	Performed as expected	Passed

Table 28.12

UNIT TESTING – AQUAPONIC FARMER

Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F83	Notify Air Humidity High Threshold	Display Notifications in Notification Fragment	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F84	Notify Air Humidity Low Threshold	Display Notifications in Notification Fragment	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F85	Notify DHT Sensor Status Off	Display Notifications in Notification Fragment	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F86	Notify Ultrasonic Plant Sensor Status Off	Display Notifications in Notification Fragment	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F87	Show Push Notification pH Level High Threshold	Display Notification in phone	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F88	Show Push Notification pH Level Low Threshold	Display Notification in phone	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F89	Show Push Notification pH Sensor Status Off	Display Notification in phone	Performed as expected	Passed

Table 28.13

UNIT TESTING – AQUAPONIC FARMER

Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F90	Show Push Notification TDS Level High Threshold	Display Notification in phone	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F91	Show Push Notification TDS Level Low Threshold	Display Notification in phone	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F92	Show Push Notification TDS Sensor Status Off	Display Notification in phone	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F93	Show Push Notification Water Temperature High Threshold	Display Notification in phone	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F94	Show Push Notification Water Temperature Low Threshold	Display Notification in phone	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F95	Show Push Notification Water Temperature Sensor Status Off	Display Notification in phone	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F96	Show Push Notification Water Level High Threshold	Display Notification in phone	Performed as expected	Passed

Table 28.14

UNIT TESTING – AQUAPONIC FARMER

Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F97	Show Push Notification Water Level Low Threshold	Display Notification in phone	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F98	Show Push Notification Water Level Sensor Status Off	Display Notification in phone	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F99	Show Push Notification Air Temperature High Threshold	Display Notification in phone	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F100	Show Push Notification Air Temperature Low Threshold	Display Notification in phone	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F101	Show Push Notification Air Humidity High Threshold	Display Notification in phone	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F102	Show Push Notification Air Humidity Low Threshold	Display Notification in phone	Performed as expected	Passed
Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F103	Show Push Notification DHT Sensor Status Off	Display Notification in phone	Performed as expected	Passed

Table 28.15

UNIT TESTING – AQUAPONIC FARMER

Farm Management and Monitoring (Mobile)	View System Notifications	12/13/23	F104	Show Push Notification Ultrasonic Plant Sensor Status Off	Display Notification in phone	Performed as expected	Passed
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Table 29

UNIT TESTING – AQUAPONIC FARMER ADMIN

Module Name	Unit Name	Date Tested	Test Case ID	Test Case Description	Expected Results	Actual Results	Remarks
Login (Web)	Login as Farm Administrator	12/09/23	UT1	Missing Fields	Error Message Displayed	Perform as expected	Passed
Login (Web)	Login as Farm Administrator	12/09/23	UT2	Entered old account password	Error Message Displayed	Perform as expected	Passed
Login (Web)	Login as Farm Administrator	12/09/23	UT3	Entered active Farm Admin Account	Logged In	Perform as Expected	Passed
Reset Password (Web)	Reset Forgotten Farm Administrator Password	12/09/23	UT4	Entered a farm admin email account that was deleted	Error Message Displayed	Perform as Expected	Passed
Reset Password (Web)	Reset Forgotten Farm Administrator Password	12/09/23	UT5	Entered an active farm admin email account	Sent an email to the farm admin account	Perform as Expected	Passed
Reset Password (Web)	Reset Forgotten Farm Administrator Password	12/09/23	UT6	Entered nothing	Error message displayed	Perform as Expected	Passed

Table Number 29.1

UNIT TESTING – AQUAPONIC FARMER ADMIN

Manage Workgroup (Web)	View Workgroup Menu	12/09/23	UT7	Selected the UI panel	View all active farmers in the workgroup	Perform as Expected	Passed
Manage Workgroup (Web)	Delete a farmer	12/09/23	UT8	Deletion of a farmer account	Deleted a farmer account	Perform as Expected	Passed
Register and Manage Requests (Web)	Register a farmer	12/09/23	UT9	Entered farmer's credentials correctly	Added farmer to the workgroup	Perform as Expected	Passed
Register and Manage Requests (Web)	Register a farmer	12/09/23	UT10	Entered farmer's credentials with unmatched password	Error message displayed	Perform as Expected	Passed
Register and Manage Requests (Web)	Register a farmer	12/09/23	UT11	Entered an existing farmer's credentials	Error message displayed	Perform as Expected	Passed
Register and Manage Requests (Web)	Register a farmer	12/09/23	UT12	Entered an existing farmer's credentials with not the same password	Error message displayed	Perform as Expected	Passed
Register and Manage Requests (Web)	Register a farmer	12/09/23	UT13	Entered an existing farmer's credentials with unmatching passwords	Error message displayed	Perform as Expected	Passed
Register and Manage Requests (Web)	Approve farmers to the workgroup	12/09/23	UT14	Pressed the approved button	Added farmer to the workgroup	Perform as Expected	Passed
Register and Manage Requests (Web)	Approve farmers to the workgroup	12/09/23	UT15	Pressed the delete button	Deleted farmer's request to enter the workgroup	Perform as Expected	Passed

Table 29.2

UNIT TESTING – AQUAPONIC FARMER ADMIN

Harvest Calendar (Web)	Harvest Calendar Panel	12/09/23	UT1 6	Viewed the harvest calendar	Harvest calendar displayed	Perform as Expected	Passed
Harvest Calendar (Web)	Harvest Calendar Panel Modal	12/09/23	UT1 7	Clicked the harvest calendar itself	Modal for tweaking the harvest calendar displayed	Perform as Expected	Passed
Harvest Calendar (Web)	Harvest Calendar Panel Modal	12/09/23	UT1 8	Gave correct dates in the harvest calendar And right details for the harvest and pressed the set harvest button	Harvest calendar definitions left changed	Perform as Expected	Passed
Harvest Calendar (Web)	Harvest Calendar Panel Modal	12/09/23	UT1 9	Gave incorrect dates in the harvest calendar And incomplete and pressed the set harvest button details for the harvest	Harvest calendar definitions left unchanged	Perform as Expected	Passed
Harvest Calendar (Web)	Harvest Calendar Panel Modal	12/09/23	UT2 0	Gave empty requests for the harvest calendar and pressed the set harvest button	Harvest calendar definitions unchanged	Perform as Expected	Passed
Notifications Panel (Web)	Notification Panel Modal	12/09/23	UT2 1	Clicked the notifications panel	Panel displayed the notifications	Perform as Expected	Passed

Table 29.3

UNIT TESTING – AQUAPONIC FARMER ADMIN

Aquatic Sensors Status (Web)	Aquatic Sensors Status Panel	12/09/23	UT2 2	Clicked the Aquatic Sensors Panel	Aquatic Sensors Panel graph statistics were shown	Perform as Expected	Passed
Aquatic Sensors Status (Web)	Aquatic Sensors Status Panel	12/09/23	UT2 3	Clicked the zoom in and zoom out buttons for the graphs	Aquatic Sensors Panel graph statistics were shown in a zoomed manner	Perform as Expected	Passed
Terrestrial Sensors Status (Web)	Terrestrial Sensors Status Panel	12/09/23	UT2 4	Clicked the Terrestrial Sensors Panel	Terrestrial Sensors Panel graph statistics were shown	Perform as Expected	Passed
Terrestrial Sensors Status (Web)	Terrestrial Sensors Status Panel	12/09/23	UT2 5	Clicked the zoom in and zoom out buttons for the graphs	Terrestrial Sensors Panel graph statistics were shown in a zoomed manner	Perform as Expected	Passed
Adjust System Thresholds (Web)	Adjust System Thresholds Panel	12/09/23	UT2 6	Clicked the zoom in and zoom out buttons for the graphs	Viewed the previously given system parameters in the panel	Perform as Expected	Passed

Table 29.4

UNIT TESTING – AQUAPONIC FARMER ADMIN

Adjust System Thresholds (Web)	Adjust System Thresholds Panel	12/09/23	UT2 7	Clicked/adjusted on the value for a certain parameter and didn't click the save configuration button	System parameters left unchanged.	Perform as Expected	Passed
Adjust System Thresholds (Web)	Adjust System Thresholds Panel	12/09/23	UT2 8	Clicked/adjusted on the value for a certain parameter and clicked the save configuration button	System parameters left changed and viewed the results immediately.	Perform as Expected	Passed
Technical Support (Web)	Technical Support Panel	12/09/23	UT2 9	Clicked on the accordions for each individual FAQs	View troubleshooting options	Perform as Expected	Passed
Technical Support (Web)	About System Button	12/09/23	UT3 0	Clicked on the about system button	View credits and system's versions	Perform as Expected	Passed
Logout (Web)	Logout Button on the Panel	12/09/23	UT3 1	Clicked on the logout button	Logged user out	Perform as Expected	Passed
Logout (Web)	Logout Button on the Panel	12/09/23	UT3 2	Clicked on the logout button	Logged user out	Perform as Expected	Passed
Light/Dark Mode Button (Web)	Light/Dark Mode Button on the global panel	12/09/23	UT3 3	Clicked on the button	System UI changed	Perform as Expected	Passed

Table 29.5

UNIT TESTING – AQUAPONIC FARMER ADMIN

Profile Button (Web)	Profile Button on the global panel	12/09/23	UT3 4	Clicked on the Profile button	Viewed Profile	Perform as Expected	Passed
Edit Profile Button (Web)	Profile Button on the Panel	12/09/23	UT3 5	Clicked on the Profile button	Viewed Profile Panel	Perform as Expected	Passed
Profile Panel (Web)	Edit Profile Panel	12/09/23	UT3 6	Clicked on the Edit Profile button	Show edit profile modal	Perform as Expected	Passed
Profile Panel (Web)	Edit Profile Panel Modal	12/09/23	UT3 7	Clicked on the Save Changes button without any new data	Farm admin's profile left unchanged	Perform as Expected	Passed
Profile Panel (Web)	Edit Profile Panel Modal	12/09/23	UT3 8	Added a valid image with valid format	Farm admin's profile picture definitions updated	Perform as Expected	Passed
Profile Panel (Web)	Edit Profile Panel Modal	12/09/23	UT3 9	Added a valid image with invalid format	Farm admin's profile picture left unchanged	Perform as Expected	Passed
Profile Panel (Web)	Edit Profile Panel Modal	12/09/23	UT4 0	Changed the farm admin's name	Farm admin's full name changed	Perform as Expected	Passed
Profile Panel (Web)	Edit Profile Panel Modal	12/09/23	UT4 1	Cancel button clicked	Farm admin's profile left unchanged	Perform as Expected	Passed
Profile Panel (Web)	Change Password Modal	12/09/23	UT4 2	Entered matching password and confirm password	Farm admin's password changed	Perform as Expected	Passed

Table 29.6

UNIT TESTING – AQUAPONIC FARMER ADMIN

Profile Panel (Web)	Change Password Modal	12/09/23	UT4 3	Entered unmatching password and confirm password	Farm admin's password left unchanged and error message is displayed	Perform as Expected	Passed
Profile Panel (Web)	Change Password Modal	12/09/23	UT4 4	Entered nothing	Farm admin's password left unchanged and error message is displayed	Perform as Expected	Passed
Profile Panel (Web)	Change Password Modal	12/09/23	UT4 5	Entered lacking fields	Error message is displayed	Perform as Expected	Passed

Integration Testing

Integration testing is a software test unit that combines and tests individual units as a group. The aim of this stage is to identify errors in the interaction of embedded units. The table below demonstrates the two modules integration and would produce good outcomes if running together.

Table 30

INTEGRATION TESTING TABLE

Test Case ID	Module 1	Integration Process	Module 2	Precondition	Results	Remarks
IT1	Sign Up (Mobile)	Sign Up with invalid credentials	Approve Farmer's Request – Approve (Web)	The farmer has provided all details correctly.	Perform as expected.	Passed

Table Number 30.1
INTEGRATION TESTING TABLE

IT2	Sign Up (Mobile)	Sign Up with invalid credentials	Approve Farmer's Request - Delete Request (Web)	The farmer has "provided" all details "correctly".	Perform as expected.	Passed
IT3	Sign In (Mobile)	Sign in with valid credentials	Manage workgroup	The farmer has been approved by the farm admin.	Perform as expected.	Passed
IT4	Sign In (Mobile)	Sign in with invalid credentials	Manage workgroup	The farmer has been approved by the farm admin.	Perform as expected. The farmer can sign in approved.	Passed
IT5	Sign In (Mobile)	Sign in with valid credentials	Manage workgroup-Delete account	The farmer has been approved by the farm admin.	Perform as expected. Deleted and inactivated farmer account and farmer is unable to login.	Passed
IT6	Sign In (Mobile)	Farmer has given correct credentials to the farm admin	Register Farmer Account	The farmer has consented in giving their credentials to the farm admin	Perform as expected. Farmer is able to login without any further approvals from the farm admin.	Passed
IT7	Harvest Calendar (Mobile)	Farmer will be able to see the harvest calendar as set by the admin	Harvest Calendar (Web)	The farm admin has set the harvest calendar of the workgroup	Perform as expected. Farmer is able to see the harvest calendar.	Passed

Table Number 30.2
INTEGRATION TESTING TABLE

IT8	Harvest Calendar (Web)	Farm admin updates the harvest calendar	Harvest Calendar (Mobile)	The workgroup is existent	Perform as expected. Farmer is able to see the updates in the harvest calendar.	Passed
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Alpha Testing

Alpha Testing is described as a kind of software testing carried out to detect bugs before releasing the item to actual customers or the public. It is a form of screening for acceptance. This test is called an alpha test only because it is performed early on, near the end of software development, and before beta testing.

Table 31
ALPHA TESTING – TABLE

Test Criteria	Poor	Fair	Good	Very Good
Graphical User Interface (GUI)				
Consistency (The user interface is of the same formatting style and icons throughout the system)			✓	
Reusability (The system contains reusable GUI components such as familiar buttons, text and checkboxes, and other tools.)				✓
Forgiveness and Tolerance (The interface displays message or confirmation prompts that would allow user to undo or redo critical actions.)			✓	
Simplicity (The GUI design include simple GUI buttons, such as simple screens with clear, uncrowded messages.)			✓	
Clarity (Displayed error, help, and warning messages are clear, concise, and as elementary as possible to assist user in operating the software.)			✓	

Table Number 31.1
ALPHA TESTING – TABLE

Flexibility (The system includes user preference setting to allow changes, for example, increasing the font size)		✓		
User-friendliness (The GUI design must be user-friendly, by providing helpful, courteous, and non-offending messages.)			✓	
System Performance				
Conformance to the Requirements (The system effectively met all the identified features and/or requirements.)			✓	
Conformance to the Objectives (All specific objectives of the system are met by the program.)			✓	
Efficiency (The entire system functions efficiently. It doesn't have delay in any transaction.)			✓	
Security (The system is secured. Login details are authenticated. Input parameters are ensured prior to the execution of the next transaction.)				✓
Integrity (The software allows registered user to have control over its own private information.)			✓	
Overall Impression (In general, the program or system is functional and useful.)			✓	

Shown in Table 31 is the alpha testing performed on the mobile application AquaFusion. It tests the application's back-end as well as front-end section from poor to very good. This test ensures that the product is prepared before it is deployed.

Acceptance Testing

In this phase, the system was being tested for its usability to check if it really meets the business requirements identified in the previous phase. This is also, where the application is tested whether or not it is ready for the release or deployment phase.

Table 32
ACCEPTANCE TESTING

PROJECT IDENTIFICATION							
Project Name				Date Created			
AquaFusion				September 2023			
Project Sponsor / Owner				Project Manager			
AquaFusion				Elijah Nicholas Esguerra			
Project Adviser				Dean			
Mr. Eric P. Ortega				Ms. Moma D. Ortega			
ACCEPTANCE CRITERIA TEST MATRIX							
Construct	Operational Definition	Measured Items	Critical		Test Results		Comments
			Yes	No	Accept	Reject	
Perceived Ease of Use	Perceive ease of use refers to the extent to which the user believes that using the system will be free of effort.	The user believes that he/she is able to create an account easily.	✓		✓		
		The user believes that he/she is able to login to his/her account easily.	✓		✓		
		The user believes that he/she is able to use the navigation bar easily	✓		✓		
		The user believes that he/she can logout of the application easily.	✓		✓		
		The user believes that his/her interaction with the menu and notifications is clear.	✓		✓		

Table Number 32.1
ACCEPTANCE TESTING

		The user believes it is easy for him/her to understand how to use the sensor menu and notifications features.	✓		✓		
Construct	Operational Definition	Measured Items	Yes	No	Accept	Reject	Comments
Perceived Usefulness	Perceived usefulness refers to the degree which a user believes that utilizing AquaFusion will enhance their productivity and effectiveness in managing the aquaponics farm	The user believes that it enhances the monitoring and control of key aquaponic parameters that are hard to manually track continually.	✓		✓		
		The user believes that it saves time in not having to individually check each set up daily, enabled by centralized remote monitoring.	✓		✓		
		The user believes that he/she have the ability to respond to changes faster based on real-time alerts and notifications	✓		✓		

Table Number 32.2
ACCEPTANCE TESTING

Construct	Operational Definition	Measured Items	Yes	No	Accept	Reject	Comments
Attitude Towards Using	Attitude towards using refers to the user's general feeling of favorable or unfavorable for the use of the system	The user believes that it has perceived alignment of the monitoring system's capabilities to the user's specific needs and priorities for their aquaponics farm management.	✓		✓		
		The user believes that it has affective judgement on how utilizing the technology can enhance satisfaction through making their responsibilities easier and improving productivity.	✓		✓		
		The user believes that it has internal valuation of the financial, time, and effort tradeoffs in adopting the system versus traditional methods.	✓		✓		

Table Number 33.3
ACCEPTANCE TESTING

OTHER CONSIDERATIONS		
Business Objectives – Did the software application/system meet the business objectives?		
Yes ✓	No	The AquaFusion meets the business objectives
Does the software/application/system require any changes prior to installation? If so, please describe.		
Yes	No ✓	
APPROVAL		
Project Sponsor/Project Owner	Signature	Date
Yes ✓	No	December 16, 2023

Implementation/Deployment Phase

The system was implemented to the actual users during their respective environments implementation and deployment phase. All specification requirements, including software, hardware, and human resources, are identified thoroughly explained. Step-by-step instructions on using the application on their respective mobile phones were provided. The target goal and why the application was created were elaborated correctly so that users understood the application’s purpose.

Deployment Diagram

Figure 55: AquaFusion Deployment Diagram

Figure 55 shows the deployment diagram for the AquaFusion system has been structured with distinct components to accommodate farmers using the Android mobile app and administrators utilizing the web app. In the field, farmers employ the Android app on their smartphones, establishing a connection with a central application server provided by Firebase to manage essential operations and ensure secure data handling. This facilitates the retrieval and updating of farm-related information seamlessly.

For administrators working on desktops or laptops, the web app is their go-to solution, served by firebase's dedicated web server. This Web Application communicates with the same application server as the mobile app, offering administrators access to advanced features and aggregated data in a secure manner through the help of the Backend Application which is deployed as a cloud function. With all of this, both the web and mobile apps rely on a centralized database server, guaranteeing the persistent storage and retrieval of farm-related information. The deployment architecture is meticulously designed to optimize resource allocation, streamlining the flow of data and functionality between the distinct user interfaces and the underlying servers.

Implementation Budget/Cost Specification

This section shows the expenses spend during the implementation of the application.

TABLE 33
COST SPECIFICATION

Items	Unit	Amount
Tool:		
Raspberry Pi 4 Model B 4GB	1	₱6,508
DS18B20 Water Temperature Sensor	1	₱99
HC-SR04 Ultrasonic Sensor	2	₱89
DHT22 Temperature and Humidity Sensor	1	₱195
TDS Analog Sensor	1	₱599
PH-4502C Liquid PH Sensor with E201-BNC pH Electrode	1	₱999
ADS1115 16-Bit ADC	2	₱100
TCA9548A I2C Multiplexer	1	₱278
16x2 Liquid Crystal Displays	2	₱100

TABLE 33.1
COST SPECIFICATION

PH + TDS EC Meter	1	₱297
pH Up & Down Phosphorus Based pH Adjuster	1	₱245
pH Meter Calibration Buffer Solution	2	₱135
Jumper Wires Dupont Wire Female – Female 10cm 10pcs	1	₱50
Jumper Wires Dupont Wire Male – Female 10cm 10pcs	2	₱50
Jumper Wires Dupont Wire Male – Male 10cm 10pcs	1	₱50
Perfboard 15x18	3	₱35
Google Firebase	1	Free
Total:		₱10,373

Table 33 shows the specific expenses rendered by the team during the implementation. The first tool is the hardware used in the system's development. Raspberry Pi 4 is one of the crucial hardware that the team needs during the development stage. Following are the sensors that must be applied and used in a synchronous manner with the Raspberry Pi 4 to enable the proponents to implement the necessary codes that are needed on local which is Python and to connect to Firebase, it uses Firebase Python Admin SDK. The proponents utilized PH Adjuster and Buffer Solutions to tweak the water's PH level in order to achieve a neutral PH concentration. Once the desired concentration is achieved, the researchers then take samples from the concentrated water to condition the sensors in such a way that the sensors would be able to accurately alarm the user when the PH levels have fluctuated or returned to a neutral PH level of 7. The Dupont Wires are needed to connect the GPIO Pin header to the respective sensors and also to mapped the circuitry to the Perfboard for soldering.

Software Specification

In this system, the team used relevant, ubiquitous, and open-source frameworks and tools to build web and mobile applications. With this, issues and problems arising from support or

security can quickly be resolved with documentation for its usage found online. With this, for the mobile application, AquaFusion is developed using the native Android SDK that supports Android 8.0 (Oreo) up until Android 14, both for the front-end and back-end sides. On the other hand, AquaFusion's front-end web application primarily uses React and Material UI Design which supports modern browsers. In addition, for the back-end portion of the web application, Express is used to write the middleware, which serves as the bridge for the front end of the database with the primary purpose of manipulating the data. With mobile and web applications in place, the data is inside Firebase's NoSQL Firestore database. As the web application is built almost entirely with Javascript, the server has a JavaScript runtime to run the Express middleware and ReactJ front-end. On the other hand, the IoT device should have an Ubuntu Raspberry Pi 22.04 environment installed and Python3 runtime installed to process data coming from the I/O and, finally, for the system's deployment. The web application's repository would be GitHub to quickly deploy the page through Hostman, a cloud service provider promising to host websites written in Javascript, requiring a repository to import the websites' source codes. In addition to this, the chosen domain name is GoDaddy.

Hardware Specification

For the hardware support of the system, the team decided to go with the bare minimum to ensure that the software can run even with low-specification devices. With this, the system will be more accessible even to older designs. Though this doesn't apply directly to the IoT device as these use the latest SoCs that the Raspberry Pi foundation has released, however, for the mobile application requires that the device has an Android 8.0 (Oreo) installed, with an ARM processor that is capable of running at 1.5GHz, and with 2 GB available RAM together with 3Gb of open installation space. The web application requires the system to have a Chromium-derived or a Firefox browser with JavaScript enabled. Lastly, the IoT device needs the receiving system on a Raspberry Pi 4 with 32 GB available space to compensate for the operating system installation with various runtime. With all of these, the system connected to the internet, preferably through the Raspberry Pi's Wi-Fi, effectively the data to the cloud in real-time.

Human Resources Specification

This section refers to the different human resources involved or needed to develop the proposed application. The individuals involved in creating the application are the programmers, UI designers, database designers, circuit diagram designer, aquaponic farmers and practitioners. The programmers are the people in-charge in implementing the application through coding using the

required platform for development. The UI designer is in charge of designing the application's user interfaces for aquaponic farmers, practitioners and admin side. Circuit diagram designer is in charge of designing the schematics of the hardware components from the Raspberry Pi 4 to the sensors that will be used to maximize efficiency and lessen the risk of hardware failure. The system analyst or database designer is in charge of checking all the parts of the system if it coordinates well based on the traceable software requirements specification. Finally, the aquaponic farmers and practitioners are also needed to develop the data inputs needed to test the application in the testing phase successfully.

User Guide

Depending on the type of user, this section offers a user guide to assist the users in navigating around the application.

1. Introduction

AquaFusion is a an IoT-based system focuses on monitoring the development and deployment of a comprehensive monitoring solution for aquaponic systems. The mobile application's key feature is the real-time monitoring of parameters and timely alerts and notifications of any fluctuation and deviation of a certain parameter. Moreover, it caters a graph to envisage parameters for further visualization of data.

2. System Summary

2.1 System Configuration

AquaFusion runs on devices such as mobile phones, tablets, and other electronic devices as long as it has an android operating system. The AquaFusion is compatible with version 8 of Android (Oreo) and up to the latest release. The application requires you to have an Internet connection. The application requires you to have an Internet connection.

2.2 User Access Levels

Users who have registered through the app and AquaFusion website can only use the mobile application.

3. Installation

Once the Farm Administrator registered the user, the Farm Administrator will request the APK installer file from the super administrators.

4. User Manual

1. Tap the login button if user has an account.
2. Input user credentials (email and password).

3. Tap the register link if user has no account.
4. Tap the forgot password link if user has forgotten their password.

5. Input user credentials (workgroup ID, name, email, password, and confirm password).
6. Tap register button for user account approval.
7. Tap the login link to navigate back to login page.

8. Input email address.
9. Tap the continue button to send reset password link from Gmail/Yahoo.

10. Tap view sensor details to view descriptive information about the sensors.
11. Tap view sensor status to see if the sensors are on or off.
12. Tap view system thresholds to view the system thresholds set by the farmer admin.
13. Tap view sensor data graph to see the visual presentations of the sensor data.
14. Tap the back to sensor menu button to go back to sensor menu.
15. Tap select date to view the pH level, water temperature, etc. on the graph on the chosen date.
16. Tap the “?” button to view the descriptive information about the graph.
17. Tap the back navigation of the phone to go back to sensor menu.

14. 15. 16. 17. 18.

18. Tap the sensor icon to access sensor menu page.
19. Tap the plant icon to access plant growth monitoring page.
20. Tap the calendar icon to access harvest calendar page.

21. Tap the notification icon to access system notifications page.
22. Tap the profile icon to access profile page.

23. Tap select date to view the plant growth level on the graph on the chosen date.
24. Tap the “?” button to view the descriptive information about the graph.
25. Tap view harvest calendar button to access calendar.
26. Tap ok or cancel to exit calendar.

27. Toggle on the push notification switch to enable/disable notification app permission.

28. Tap edit profile button to edit profile information.

29. Tap change password button to change user password.

30. Tap view help and about application link to access app information.
31. Tap logout session button to logout.
32. Tap upload image to change profile image.
33. Input new name to change name.
34. Tap save changes button to save profile changes.
35. Tap cancel to cancel profile changes.

36. Input current password.
37. Tap continue button to proceed change password page.
38. Input new password.
39. Tap save changes to save new password.
40. Tap cancel to cancel changes.

41. Tap view technical support link to access technical support page.

42. Tap arrow down icon to view answer.

43. Tap arrow up icon to hide answer.

Installation Guide

The installation guide helps the users with the installation of the mobile application in their android phones, tablets, and the like.

1. Check device requirements
 - a. Device must at least have an OS Android Version 8.0 (Oreo).
 - b. Device must be connected to the Internet.
2. Install the application
 - a. Request the APK installer file from the super administrators.
 - b. To enable the installation of the AquaFusion Mobile App using an APK, go to the Android settings and enable 'Unknown Sources' in the applications section.

Project Roadmap

The project roadmap is a high-level, easy-to-understand overview of the important pieces of a project. It shows the project's goals and ambitions.

Figure 56: AquaFusion Project Roadmap

Figure 56 presents the AquaFusion application's project roadmap where the researchers display the different deliverables to be achieved given a specific duration of activities in the timeline. It includes the series of events of the application on what are the strategies and enhancements that will be made, starting with adding more features and integrating new sensors and refined architecture. For the 1st quarter of 2024, the project team will review and refine the project scope and objectives, ensuring alignment with the evolving needs of the Aquaponic Monitoring System. Additionally, they will focus on finalizing the comprehensive list of sensors and monitoring parameters essential for precise data collection and system functionality. Simultaneously, efforts will begin to integrate these new sensors seamlessly into the existing system architecture, laying the foundation for enhanced monitoring capabilities. For the 2nd quarter of 2024, the project team will prioritize system robustness by implementing rigorous data validation and error-checking mechanisms, ensuring the accuracy and reliability of the aquaponic data collected. Simultaneously, the team will enhance the user experience through the implementation of new dashboard components, offering insightful and user-friendly visualizations of the aquaponic system's performance. Moreover, comprehensive testing will be conducted across a variety of Android devices and versions to ensure seamless functionality and broad compatibility. For the 3rd quarter, the project team will shift their focus towards optimizing the system's performance by fine-tuning database queries, thereby ensuring faster and more efficient data retrieval. Additionally, they will invest time in comprehensive documentation of the API, creating a valuable resource for future reference and facilitating third-party integrations seamlessly. Simultaneously, the team will conduct meticulous testing procedures to guarantee the system's ability to deliver timely and accurate notifications, enhancing the overall reliability of the Aquaponic Monitoring System. For the 4th quarter of 2024, the project team will engage in a thorough evaluation of the system's performance under varying loads, identifying and implementing optimizations as necessary to maintain efficient operation. In parallel, the team will undertake a rigorous assessment of data privacy measures, ensuring that the Aquaponic Monitoring System is fully compliant with relevant regulations, safeguarding user data and system integrity. Additionally, the team will conduct comprehensive training sessions, equipping end-users and administrators with the knowledge and skills required for effective system operation and management.

Conclusion

Based on the data gathered, the proponents concluded that automated monitoring system is in demand by the aquaponic farmers and practitioners due to the fact that traditional monitoring is laborious and also time intensive. It is also not accurate and sometimes they cannot log the parameters since they also have another errand and that makes the aquaponic farmers and practitioners have low yields and unoptimized setup to grow aquaponics. Lastly, the AquaFusion application is a practical application that can help lessen the labor and effortlessly monitor the aquaponic setup even when the farmer or practitioner is on the go or at the farm.

Recommendation

The proponents eyed all the possible room for improvements in this application, such as:

1. Ensuring AquaFusion to scale easily to accommodate more sensors, devices, and users as the system expands.
2. Implementing advanced data analytics and machine learning algorithms to gain predictive insights into aquaponic system behavior.
3. Continuously improve the user interface and experience of the mobile application.
4. Exploring opportunities to integrate with Internet of Things (IoT) devices, such as smart pumps or automated feeders, to further enhance the automation and control capabilities of the aquaponic system.
5. Create a platform for users to share their aquaponic setups, data, and experiences. This can foster a sense of community among aquaponics enthusiasts and encourage knowledge exchange.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A

Transmittal Letter – Fund Development Officer

July 20, 2023

Ms. Florence Camillo
Fund Development Officer
SOS Children's Village, Highway 11, Talamban, Cebu City

Dear Ms. Camilio,

Greetings!

We, the 4th year Bachelor of Science in Information Technology Students of the University of Cebu – Banilad Campus, would like to conduct a survey related to our study entitled “AquaFusion: An IoT-Based Monitoring System”. An Internet of Things (IoT), mobile and web-based application for aquaponic farmer and practitioners for monitoring purposes.

Rest assured that the data gathered will be kept confidential and will be used for educational purposes only.

Sincerely,

Elijah Nicholas Esguerra
Project Manager

Noted By:

Mr. Eric P. Ortega

Adviser

Ms. Monica D. Ortega

Dean, College of Computer Studies

Appendix B

Transmittal Letter – Hydroponics Farmer

August 1, 2023

Mr. Arnold R. Ybañez
Hydroponics Farmer
1069-8 Kalubihan Talamban, Cebu City

Dear Mr. Ybañez,

Greetings!

We, the 3rd year Bachelor of Science in Information Technology Students of the University of Cebu – Banilad Campus, would like to conduct a survey related to our study entitled “AquaFusion: An IoT-Based Monitoring System”. An Internet of Things (IoT), mobile and web-based application for aquaponic farmer and practitioners for monitoring purposes.

Rest assured that the data gathered will be kept confidential and will be used for educational purposes only.

Sincerely,

Elijah Nicholas Esguerra
Project Manager

Noted By:

Mr. Eric P. Ortega
Adviser

Ms. Moma D. Ortega
Dean, College of Computer Studies

Transmittal Letter – City Agriculturist

August 3, 2023

Mr. Bernard Quijano
City Agriculturist
LGU City of Talisay
Lawaan II, City of Talisay, Cebu

Dear Mr. Quijano,

Greetings!

We, the 3rd year Bachelor of Science in Information Technology Students of the University of Cebu – Banilad Campus, would like to conduct a survey related to our study entitled “AquaFusion: An IoT-Based Monitoring System”. An Internet of Things (IoT), mobile and web-based application for aquaponic farmer and practitioners for monitoring purposes.

Rest assured that the data gathered will be kept confidential and will be used for educational purposes only.

Sincerely,

Elifan Nicholas Esguerra
Project Manager

Noted By:

Mr. Erie P. Ortega
Capstone Adviser

Ms. Moma D. Ortega
Dean, College of Computer Studies

Appendix D**Research Instrument**

To obtain data for developing IoT-based applications, the researcher will use an actual interview guide. Researchers will use prior studies, application performance, and technical literature to inform the researcher's readings. Researchers will create an actual questionnaire that aligns with the objectives, focusing on gathering data about the problems and difficulties related to maintaining the ambient conditions of the aquaponic farm. The criteria for designing efficient data gathering instruments are evaluated in preparation for the device. Researchers will ask open-ended questions to allow for unbiased opinions on the application or concerns about the application that will be used. After interviewing the aquaponic farmers or practitioners, the instrument will be able to acquire helpful information. Visiting the farm and having an actual interview face-to-face will be based on several research assumptions and providing respondents with a higher sense of privacy. Furthermore, the instrument was validated by the subject instructor before the analysis.

Appendix E**Interview Guide**

I am a student at the University of Cebu – Banilad, taking up Bachelor of Science in Information Technology. I am currently conducting a study entitled: “AquaFusion: An IoT-Based Monitoring System”. In line with this, I am requesting you to spare a few minutes of your time to answer this questionnaire honestly. Rest assured that all the answers will be treated with the utmost confidentiality.

1. What are your experiences with aquaponics/hydroponics system?
2. What are your goals of having an aquaponic/hydroponics system?
 - To grow own food
 - To save water
 - To reduce environmental impact
 - Others:
3. How long have you been using the aquaponics/hydroponics system?
 - Less than 1 year
 - 1-3 years
 - 3-5 years
 - 5+ years
4. How often do you monitor your system?
 - Daily
 - Weekly
 - Monthly
 - Others:
5. What do you monitor often in your system?

- pH level
 - Water Level
 - Temperature
 - Plant Growth
6. What are the challenges you have faced with your system?
- Water Quality
 - Plant Growth
 - Fish Health
 - Others:
7. What type of data do you collect from your system?
8. What are your thoughts on your current setup of your system?
- It's working well
 - I'm having some problems
 - I'm not sure
9. What are the strengths and weaknesses of your current system?
10. What features would you like to see in your future system?
- Automatic Monitoring
 - Remote Control
 - Data Analytics
11. What are your thoughts on using sensors to monitor your system?
- I'm interested in using sensors
 - I'm not sure about using sensors
 - I don't want to use sensors
12. What are your thoughts on automating the controls of your system?

- I'm interested in automating controls
- I'm not sure about automating controls
- I don't want to automate controls

13. What are your thoughts on data analytics to improve your system?

- I'm interested in using data analytics
- I'm not sure about using data analytics
- I don't want to use data analytics

Appendix F

Results and Findings

The following findings are based on data acquired from the proponents' and respondents' interviews and surveys.

What are your experiences with aquaponics/hydroponics system?

10 responses

They are sensitive and needs proper monitoring. Water, levels of dissolved substances, the humidity, and the pH are monitored twice a day. Because a single mistake in the figures relating to these parameters induces an effect to the entire system.

a bit excitement and challenging

kapoy kay bantayonon jud kaau pero worth it ra kay naa nay pang samgyup, ang meat nalay gastuonon hahah

It is a fulfilling experience in a sense that lettuce farming is made possible thru hydroponics technology. The videos we admire in Youtube became a financial reality.

Small scale pa lang maong dili kaayo daghan ug yield pero sa tanan nga amo gi tanom, mostly mi turok ra tanan

We are happy and glad since we grow our own food and also the harvest that we have, we share it to our Churchmates and also to our neighbors.

There are times that I enjoyed it and there are times that I am worried.

Ma worried ko kay mo hinay ang tubo if ma stress tungod sa root rot

We've been trying hydroponics first but when we saw a video in YouTube that there is a hybrid style of harvesting, we implement the aquaponics but it is quite hard since you cannot put a lot of chemicals in it.

It is quite hard since we are hydroponics farm in the first place and we converted to aquaponics.

What are your goals of having an aquaponic/hydroponics system?

[Copy](#)

10 responses

- To grow own food
- To save water
- To reduce environmental impact
- To tell you the truth, first, having this hydroponics system was a blessing. P...
- all of the above
- For additional source of income
- To be able to sell our products
- To grow own food and to commercialize our product

How long have you been using aquaponics/hydroponics system?

[Copy](#)

10 responses

- Less than 1 year
- 1-3 years
- 3-5 years
- 5+ years

How often do you monitor your system?

[Copy](#)

10 responses

- Daily
- Weekly
- Monthly
- all of the above

What do you monitor often in your system?

[Copy](#)

10 responses

- pH level
- Water Volume
- Temperature
- Plant Growth
- All of the above
- all of the above since they are essential to our part
- We monitor our hydroponics system t...
- pH level and TDS(Turbidity)
- pH level and Turbidity

What are the challenges you have faced with your system?

[Copy](#)

10 responses

- Water quality
- Plant growth
- Fish health
- luck of sunlight that affect plant growth
- Weather condition, and Limited Time in Monitoring
- We cannot synthetically enhance our plants since it can affect the fishes
- the gradual shifting of hydroponics to aquaponics because we cannot put m...

What type of data do you collect from your system?

10 responses

We usually collect the names of the people who were checking on the system at a specific time and date, the water volume, the pH level at those times, the amount of TDS (Total Dissolved Solids), the air temperature, and the humidity of the system.

Ph level, PPM, water volume, temperature, types insects and fungus

water volume and pHLevel

PH Level, Temperature and Water Volume

Usually mag collect mi ug PPM, pH level and temperature

Water volume and pH level

Days before sowing

Sowing and day of germinating

ph Level, water volume

phLevel, temperature, turbidity

What are your thoughts on your current setup of your system?

 Copy

10 responses

- It's working well
- I'm having some problems.
- I'm not sure
- The current system is good however we would welcome new approaches that would be beneficial and cost effective

What are the strengths and weaknesses of your current system?

10 responses

I can say that the strength of our system is that we are not renting anything including the labor. In addition, I am happy to say that this system of ours is supported like we are a family; from the nanay, from the bata and because of this there is little to no misunderstandings and mis perhaps as they all know how to play their part in taking good care in the system. On the other hand, our weakness is the limited amount of funding for our system. That is why we are really needed to sell out all of our harvests so that it doesn't go to waste.

strength is we grow our own fresh food and we are learning more about the system. weaknesses expensive on starting and need focus and studies collecting data.

.

Our strengths are:

1. Learning thru the social media platform which made it easy: and
2. Accessibility of resources thru online shopping

Our weaknesses are:

1. Limitation in the physical monitoring since we are likewise busy with our other community services

We grow the food in our own ways unya dili sad need na nga mo palit mi outside. Weakness is on how our system is being setup kay dili pa siya ingon dako

The strengths of our setup is the accessibility of raw materials that we use on our system and also to our peers. The weaknesses of our setup is the strenuous monitoring it is not our main errand everyday.

Will to continue "laban lang" since the moment mo give up ko, it's over na dayun.

Eager to grow more but hesitant because I lack of experience.

The strengths are our location because we are abundant of water and natural resources therefore we can save of buying the raw materials. Our weakness are the ability to monitor frequently.

Strengths:

Natural Resources
Unlimited supply of water
Internet oriented system

Weaknesses:

Monitoring
Shifting from hydroponics to aquaponics

What features would you like to see in your future system? Copy

10 responses

 Copy

10 responses

 Copy

10 responses

Appendix G

Consultation Logs – Adviser

University of Cebu
College of Computer Studies
Capstone41 (Capstone Project 1) Consultation Logs Form

Capstone Project Title: Aquafusion: An IoT-Based Aquaponics Monitoring System

Name of Proponents: Esguerra, Elisha Nicholas
Villena, Jynaster II
Vallente, Janine Christine

Group Name: _____

Consultations	Date and Time of Consultation	Project Manager's Signature	Adviser's Signature
1st Consultation should be within	<u>09/18/23, 12:30 PM</u> Remarks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revise tech stack because of deprecated packages. • Convert backend/middleware programming language from Javascript to Typescript. • Comply with ECMA standard for Middleware. • Enhance ERD. 		
Chapter 1 must be completely delivered for adviser's evaluation			
2nd Consultation should be within	<u>09/26/23, 1:30 PM</u> Remarks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refactor Android Application from Java to Kotlin • Start meeting Sir David for the design & building of the IoT system • Integrate Typescript backend to ReactJS frontend. 		
Chapter 1 and 2 must be completely delivered for adviser's evaluation			
3rd Consultation should be within	<u>11/13/23, 9:00 AM</u> Remarks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suggestion: Add color indicator in alert's app. • Add ways to implement auth in forgot password 		
Chapter 1, 2, and 3 must be completely delivered for adviser's evaluation			
4th Consultation should be within	Remarks:		
Chapter 1, 2, 3 including initial and final pages must be completely delivered for adviser's evaluation			

This is to certify that I have been regularly consulted by my advisees, have reviewed their system prototype as well as the required manuscript of the above-stated study. As their adviser, I therefore submit them ready for Proposal Hearing as the Chapters 1 through 3 and the pertinent parts of their manuscript are complete.

NOTE: Defense Week

Signed: EM Villena
(Signature of Adviser over printed name)

Appendix H

Consultation Logs – Censors

College of Computer Studies

Capstone42 (Capstone Project 2) Consultation Logs Form

Capstone Project Title: AquaFusion : An IoT-Based Aquaponics Monitoring System

Name of Proponents: Elijah Nicholas Ecuerra
Shadester Ursara Jr
Jannet Christine Vallente

Group Name: _____

Consultations	Date and Time of Consultation	Project Manager's Signature	Censor's Signature
1st Consultation should be within _____	<u>December 15, 2025</u> Remarks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finished Manuscript / Comment & Suggestions - Architectural Layout Description - Deployment Program Description - What's New - Installation Guide 		
Chapter 1 must be completely delivered for adviser's evaluation			
2nd Consultation should be within _____	Remarks: _____		
Chapter 1 and 2 must be completely delivered for adviser's evaluation			
3rd Consultation should be within _____	Remarks: _____		
Chapter 1, 2, and 3 must be completely delivered for adviser's evaluation			
4th Consultation should be within _____	Remarks: _____		
Chapter 1, 2, 3 including initial and final pages must be completely delivered for adviser's evaluation			

This is to certify that I have been regularly consulted by my advisees; have reviewed their system prototype as well as the required manuscript of the above-stated study. As their adviser, I therefore submit them ready for **Proposal Hearing** as the Chapters 1 through 3 and the pertinent parts of their manuscript are complete.

Signed:
 (Signature of Censor over printed name)

NOTE: Defense Week _____

Appendix I

Censor's Certificate

University of Cebu
College of Computer Studies

Date: 12/05/23

CENSOR'S CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the undersigned has reviewed and went through all the pages of the proposed project study/research manuscript titled:

AquaFusion : An IoT-Based Aquaponics Monitoring System

as against the set of structural rules that govern the composition of *sentences, phrases, and words* in the English language as well as the technical terms, syntax (format, etc.) and semantics appropriate for the Information Technology and Computing fields.

Signed:

MIRIAM LOPEZ
Grammarians

Conforme:

Elijah Nicholas C. Esquivel
Project Manager

Noted:

EMU ONYIA
Adviser

System/Project Prototype – Progress Report Log

COLLEGE OF COMPUTER STUDIES Capstone Project 2 SYSTEM/PROJECT PROTOTYPE Progress Report Log							
Target Completion: <u>50% - 65% of the modules must be running</u> Target Date of Completion (1 st Prototype): <u>October 9, 2023</u>							
Prototype	Date and Time of Consultation with Adviser	# of Modules Fully Implemented (1 pt each)	# of Modules Partially Implemented (0.5 pt each)	Running Score	Percentage	Project Manager's Signature	Adviser's Signature
1 st Prototype/ System Output Implementation	10-16-23, 1:30 pt	0	7		50%		
REMARKS:	<adviser's overall evaluation on the current status of the team/project> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continue with Web & Mobile Implementation • Start IoT development and its integration with system. • Plan the system's deployment 						

COLLEGE OF COMPUTER STUDIES
Capstone Project 2

SYSTEM/PROJECT PROTOTYPE
Progress Report Log

Target Completion: 66% - 79% of the modules must be running

Target Date of Completion (1st Prototype): November 9, 2023

Prototype	Date and Time of Consultation with Adviser	# of Modules Fully Implemented (1 pt each)	# of Modules Partially Implemented (0.5 pt each)	Running Score	Percentage	Project Manager's Signature	Adviser's Signature
2 nd Prototype/ System Output Implementation	11/15/23	3	4		71.4 %		
REMARKS:	<p><adviser's overall evaluation on the current status of the team/project></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continue with the system's development. • Add additional functionalities to the mobile application. 						

COLLEGE OF COMPUTER STUDIES
Capstone Project 2

SYSTEM/PROJECT PROTOTYPE
Progress Report Log

Target Completion: **80% - 100% of the modules must be running**

Target Date of Completion (1st Prototype): **December 9, 2023**

Prototype	Date and Time of Consultation with Adviser	# of Modules Fully Implemented (1 pt each)	# of Modules Partially Implemented (0.5 pt each)	Running Score	Percentage	Project Manager's Signature	Adviser's Signature
3 rd Prototype/ System Output Implementation	<u>12/6/2023</u>	<u>7</u>	<u>0</u>	_____	<u>100%</u>		
REMARKS:	<p style="font-size: small; margin: 0;"><i><adviser's overall evaluation on the current status of the team/project></i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Begin testcases of the programs ranging from the mobile & web (front & backend) 2. Start formulating & building the circuitry needed for the device 3. Set necessary tasks on priority to allocate schedules. 						

Grammarly Result

Report: AQUAFUSION: AN IOT-BASED AQUAPONICS MONITORING SYSTEM

AQUAFUSION: AN IOT-BASED AQUAPONICS MONITORING SYSTEM

by Judy Ann Gimena

General metrics

95,046	13,920	1233	55 min 40 sec	1 hr 47 min
characters	words	sentences	reading time	speaking time

Score

This text scores better than 94%
of all texts checked by Grammarly

Writing Issues

415	162	253
Issues left	Critical	Advanced

Plagiarism

29
sources

2% of your text matches 29 sources on the web
or in archives of academic publications

TEAM COMPOSITION

Name: Elijah Nicholas C. Esguerra

Age: 21

Birthdate: November 17, 2001

Address: Bulacao, Talisay City, Cebu

Email: ashesg1117@gmail.com

Contact Number: 09205155537

Religion: Roman Catholic

Nationality: Filipino

Civil Status: Single

Educational Background:

TERTIARY:	University of Cebu - Banilad 2020 - Present
SECONDARY:	Saint Theresa's College – Cebu (Senior High School) 2018 - 2020 University of Cebu – Main (Junior High School) 2014 – 2018
PRIMARY:	University of Cebu - Main 2011-2014

Name: Junester Ursora II

Age: 21

Birthdate: May 19, 2002

Address: Baybay City, Leyte

Email: b2xjunester@gmail.com

Contact Number: 09560941325

Religion: Roman Catholic

Nationality: Filipino

Civil Status: Single

Educational Background:

TERTIARY:	University of Cebu - Banilad 2020 - Present
SECONDARY:	Baybay City Senior High School 2019 – 2020 University of Cebu – Pri Senior High School 2018 – 2019 Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception 2013 – 2016
PRIMARY:	Baybay II Central School 2007-2013

Name: Janine Christine M. Vallente

Age: 22

Birthdate: May 3, 2001

Address: Deca Homes Subdivision, Bacayan, Cebu City

Email: janinexvallente@gmail.com

Contact Number: 09659720805

Religion: Roman Catholic

Nationality: Filipino

Civil Status: Single

Educational Background:

TERTIARY: University of Cebu - Banilad
2020 - Present

SECONDARY: University of Cebu – Banilad (Senior High School)
2018 - 2020
Cabancalan National High School (Junior High School)
2016 – 2018
Colegio de la Inmaculada Concepcion-Cebu (Junior High School)
2014 – 2016

PRIMARY: Colegio de la Inmaculada Concepcion-Cebu
2008 – 2014